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List of abbreviations

CAPs	Collective Awareness Platforms
DIY	Do It Yourself
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement No. 780298 with the European Commission
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
IP	Intellectual Property
IPRs	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KUL	KU Leuven
Waag	Waag – Technology and Society
WP	work package (usually with the number, eg. WP1, WP2, etc.)
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (en: Centre for Social Innovation)
OD	Fab Lab Opendot

Definition

careables - an open solution that aims to improve the quality of life for people with unmet particular needs or facing physical limitations. careables are often co-designed, replicable, accessible, adjustable and shareable online using digital technologies. careables is a relatively new category, that promises more readily customized solutions and a more horizontal and collaborative approach to health and care.

In the following document we write *Careables* in cursive letters, when we talk about the project, and careables in normal letters, when we talk about the self-made open solutions for health and care.

Executive Summary

The main goal of this deliverable is to show the impact of the *Careable* activities on an individual and societal level. In our project, care receivers, healthcare professionals and makers join forces to co-create careables, which are tailor made solutions designed to better suit patients' needs.

We started experimenting with different long- and short-term formats of co-designing careables and looked into the impacts of these co-creation events (mainly described in D4.2). We created the *Careables* platform (www.careables.org) to foster communication and information exchange around our approach and documented the designed careables on the Welder platform. By the time of writing this deliverable we counted 180 documented careables on Welder, more than 20.000 visitors to the *Careables* platform, 7.000 visitors to the Welder platform, generating more than 200.000 page views. Both platforms were developed iteratively collecting user feedback in user-acceptance testings and interviews, which are documented in more detail in D3.2 of this project.

We used our dissemination channels to spread the idea of *Careables* to the main stakeholder groups (makers, health care professionals and people with specific needs), took part in maker fairs, conferences, workshops etc. and actively involved more than 100.000 people in these activities (see figure 23 in the last chapter of this document). As a result of our work, OpenDot, Waag and FabLab Kamp-Lintfort - created a FabCare group composed of fablabs with long-term experience in digital fabrication and health and care and hosted by the FabFoundation, an organisation that gathers more than 1.750 fablabs around the globe.

We were in the middle of the project, when we faced the COVID-19 situation, where the collaboration between healthcare professionals and makers suddenly became a worldwide movement to respond to shortages of big manufacturers in the healthcare sector. We tried to adapt to the new needs arising with the worldwide movement and created a selection of high quality COVID-19 related careables on our platform. We produced and created documents that might be specifically relevant for makers responding to the COVID-19 situation, e.g. a guide on how to legitimately design or reproduce open source medical devices and PPE¹.

We saw thousands of makers producing protective equipment for the healthcare sector, but were also faced with the challenge to keep these emerging collaborations sustainable. Our work showed that the *Careables* approach positively impacts our main three target groups: designers and

¹ <https://www.careables.org/resource/covid-19-and-open-source-hardware-legal-aspects-for-makers/>

A decorative graphic consisting of a solid blue horizontal line followed by four small blue dots.

makers benefit from the acquisition of digital fabrication and design-thinking skills. They were highly interested in producing solutions that have a real impact on people's lives and we even see new job profiles emerging in the future. Health professionals benefited from the *Careables* activities during the COVID-19 crisis and from trainings and workshops that aimed at introducing digital fabrication skills and demonstrating how the tailor-made, co-creation of healthcare solutions might support their daily work with patients.

Patients and users with specific needs benefited not only from a number of Careables tailor-made to their needs. Equally important, they were empowered to take the design of required healthcare solutions into their own hands, joining co-creation teams with designers and health professionals at eye level. In the three years project runtime, different scenarios emerged how digital fabrication can support all three groups in the future, where some of them depend on public and private funding, while others might become self-sustained activities to the benefit of society.

These scenarios are shortly described in the conclusions section of this deliverable and can be found in more detail in the sustainability plan of D.5.4. Finally, it is important to stress that the local *Careables* chapters, that were created in Europe and abroad (e.g. in Brazil, Ghana, Germany, Italy, Mali, Netherlands, Nepal) have very concrete plans on how to continue their work and sustain, if not increase the first impacts generated in this project.

1. Introduction

The main objectives of workpackage 4 were to monitor the performance of the project, evaluate the expected outcomes and assess its impact. With these aims, data were continually gathered and fed a set of monitoring criteria and impact metrics that have been developed in the initial stage of *Careables* and presented in D4.1. Evaluation and Impact Assessment Framework. Part of D4.1 was also a prioritization of the project objectives and a description of their implication for evaluation (see table 1). This prioritization helped to focus the evaluation activities.

Table 1: Overview of objectives and ranking of priority

Objectives	Implication for evaluation	Priority ranking
improve the accessibility of open source products	Accessibility of the platform and the open source products shared in the platform is increased if different target groups can better find, understand and communicate about <i>Careables</i> . We will rely on existing criteria for accessibility, usability and usefulness and evaluate them with <i>Careables</i> target users.	1 (highest)
foster knowledge exchange	Knowledge exchange is closely related to high quality collaborations. Potential effects of knowledge exchange are changes in knowledge/attitudes, practices and performance; all three aspects are relevant for the evaluation, as well as a better understanding of effective knowledge exchange processes.	2
establish collaboration between the communities	Quality of collaboration as defined by different studies; in the case of <i>Careables</i> collaboration can take place and be evaluated in the co-design and local working sessions as well as in the online activities; thus, both aspects need to be considered, with a focus on the local collaboration in the Fablabs.	3

allow anyone to replicate formats	Replication is closely connected to the aspect of accessibility and usability of the platform and the documentation process for careables. The evaluation of this objective will thus be aligned with the objective on accessibility.	4
improve quality of life or services provided	The dimensions of "Quality of life" are defined by different studies (e.g. Fitzpatrick et al. 1992; WHO); we can refer back to these studies and select the most suitable dimension for careables, also in alignment with the taxonomy/classification of careables. We will approach this topic mainly in a qualitative way.	5 (lowest)

In M24 of this project, we have already published an Interim Impact Assessment Report (D4.2), which had a strong focus on evaluating different short- and long-term formats that fostered the co-creation of careables between makers, health care professionals and users with specific needs. This report is seen as a continuation of what was presented in D4.2. Here we start with the evaluation of two more co-creation events of 2020, which addressed objectives 2,3 and 5 of the table above. Then we introduce the access statistics of our platforms, which bring light into reaching objective 1 and 4. In Chapter 5 to 7 we take a broader view on the impacts generated in the worldwide *Careables* Hubs, as well as the contribution to a worldwide open healthcare movement, which became especially important during the COVID-19 pandemic - in these chapters all objectives are addressed.

In detail:

Chapter 2 and 3 introduces the reader to the main evaluation results of two *Careables* events, the **HACKademy 2020 and the OpenDot Summerschool**. These evaluations are complementing event evaluations that have been described in all detail in D4.2 Interim Impact Assessment.

Chapter 4 will present the ***Careables* platform statistics**, as an indicator of acceptance and uptake of our approach.

Chapter 5 will introduce to the **COVID-19 reactions** of the maker community. We will present a number of case studies that specifically address the COVID-19 response of makers especially during the first wave.

Chapter 6 introduces the **worldwide *Careables* hub activities & impacts**. We show how the *Careables* approach evolved in the *Careables* hubs in Italy, Germany and Netherlands, and then abroad, in Brazil, Ghana and Nepal.

Chapter 7 reflects the wider impact of *Careables* on the **open healthcare movement and SDGs**.

Chapter 8 comes up with **a summary and conclusions** based on the project's activities and evaluations done over the project period.

Annex I-III introduces the details of the event evaluations and presents two main evaluation instruments applied in our project, to be re-used by the community.

Annex IV shows the currently unpublished version of our COVID19-paper

2. HACKademy 2020: Introduction and evaluation summary

2.1. Introduction to the HACKademy 2020 and evaluation procedure

The 3rd edition of the HACKademy was organised mostly online due to COVID-19 restrictions. It was kicked-off on the 6th and 7th of June 2020 via a two-day online event that was dedicated to building the teams and understanding case owner needs.

A period of 9 weeks of free working time for the co-creation teams followed after this initial event. The teams themselves freely shaped the working rhythm and processes in this period and were provided with online tools like: the Miro Board to scribble ideas and document the work progress, a Slack Channel to keep in contact with the organisational team and to exchange between team members and Big Blue Button for online video conferencing; additionally, the co-creation teams were supported by four bi-weekly online meetings of 90 minutes each amongst all participants, which served the experience exchange between the co-creation teams (17. June, 1. July, 15. July, 29. July).

From the 1st to 5th August 2020, a first face-to-face get-together in the Fablab of Beuth University was offered to those participants being in or close to Berlin to meet and prototype their careables. The weekend of the 8th and 9th August 2020 was the final weekend of the HACKademy and organised in a hybrid format – offline at the Beuth University and online for those participating remotely. The Saturday served to produce small video clips about the co-created careables and the documentation of the careables in Welder. On Sunday, all teams were invited to present their careables in front of a larger audience.

During the whole HACKademy 2020 teams could make use of a mentor - a person dedicated to supporting the team members during the co-creation process when needed.

The HACKademy 2020 was joined by

- 9 case providers,
- 21 makers, designers, engineers, etc., and
- 14 mentors who often acted as makers too.

There were the following teams:

-
- **Team Backpacker:** Worked on a construction to make a bag, which is fixed at the back of a wheelchair, better accessible.
 - **Team Shopping Trolley:** Worked on a construction to connect a wheelchair with a shopping trolley.
 - **Team “Here comes the mouse”:** Constructed an individually adaptable computer mouse.
 - **Team Rolli Navi:** Worked on a navigation system specifically for wheelchair drivers.
 - **Team Green Sun-Screen:** Worked on a mobile green screen to go for wheelchair drivers.
 - **Team Dirt-Consultant:** Worked on a construction that hinders hair and dirt to get caught in the front-wheel of a wheelchair.

The HACKademy 2020 was - comparable to the two previous HACKademies - evaluated via questionnaires and user journey interviews. Altogether 11 user journey interviews were organised and a questionnaire was sent out to participants (13 respondents).

The results of the evaluation are presented in all details in the **Annex** of this document. Here we would like to provide a summary of lessons learned from the evaluation of this new online format and also an outlook, into how future HACKademies could look like from the participants' point of view.

2.2. Summary of evaluation results of the HACKademy 2020

The results from HACKademy I and II, which are presented in Deliverable 4.2., with regard to the motivation of participation was confirmed also in the third HACKademy. We see people participating due to their desire of learning new skills in the area of digital fabrication and design thinking, to probe design thinking processes in a practical context, and participate in transdisciplinary teams that co-create health and care related projects, that help people with specific needs and address social aspects. Some of the participants mentioned the positive word-of-mouth from previous HACKademies as another reason for participation.

The most important benefits have been the learning, the joy of co-creating and the pleasure to create products that help somebody. New in this online format was that participants specifically mentioned the experience of collaborating in an online environment. They got to know a very creative environment that was set up by the HACKademy organisation team using a multitude of online tools like Miro (see Figure 1), BigBlueButton and Slack in a very professional way and also with a great team of moderators that steered collaboration processes of so many people that met together at the same time in the online world.

Thus, the Careables team has built up excellent knowledge that will be forwarded to the community via a specific publication foreseen for 2021.

Figure 1: A section of the HACKademy world, created in Miro. A place to meet, share, document, that accompanied the whole process.

Moving to the online world due to the COVID-19 pandemic, on the one hand, made the co-creation process more complex and demanding for the case owners, as team members could not meet personally to make hands-on experiences with the specific needs and work on early prototypes. So case owners needed to actively share pictures, videos, measurements, etc. with their teams so that the designers and makers could become active.

On the other hand, the online world allowed for people to join, who would have not joined otherwise, as they were living in other parts of Germany or could not commit to 10 days of intensive collaboration at a specific place. The carefully set up programme of the kick-off meeting, which supported the team building and a first understanding of the case owner's needs, was working out very well in the online world. This is a phase that needs structural support in the form of a specifically designed workshop format, but it can be held online. Other activities that worked well in the online world were bi-weekly meetings of all HACKademy participants, which supported the overall team building but also reflecting on team status, the steps taken so far and the open questions that need to be addressed, ideally by the community. These bi-weekly meetings can also serve as an occasion to provide the teams with specific input, like introductions into

design thinking methods, or how to create videos for documentation purposes, etc. To foster the quick prototyping process, an early meeting of at least some team members and the case owner in the offline world was suggested. Having this in mind, teams should ideally consist of at least 2 makers/designers who live close to the case owners' place; others could then join this onsite team remotely, contributing their ideas and specific knowledge and supporting tasks like the documentation.

So thinking about future HACKAdemy, a mixture of free working time for teams and organised structural programm is suggested. None of the teams could have imagined taking part in such collaboration processes without an initial kick-off meeting and without reflection meetings where the whole community gets together. Also, the final event was perceived as highly rewarding, even organised in a hybrid format with some being onsite in Berlin and others joining remotely.

Finally, we want to stress the potential that this approach has for case owners, not only by coming up with useful careables. Here are two selected statements of a case owner that show the benefits that go beyond the production of tailor-made careables expressed from their side:

"The whole HACKAdemy was very positive, the humanity of this event from the very beginning until the end did me good. I grew personally in the HACKAdemy, learned that I can contribute things, learned that I can have confidence in my own skills. I always thought that I can be creative, but now my creativity has proved to be enriching even in a technical field of work. Other makers accepted my suggestions at eye level. As I have been on sick-leave for a year, it felt very good to work again, to feel valuable, and have a task. I am very proud of the outcome. And it felt great to present it to others. It was very exciting but also very tiring. I feel enthused by the Hackadmey". HACKAdemy 2020 case owner, female

"If you are always the last link in the chain, someone that always has to be taken care of, then it is nice to be able to give input and contribute with valuable insights! Basically, the whole event is incredibly awesome." HACKAdemy 2020 case owner, male

3. OpenDot SummerSchool: Introduction and evaluation summary

The second edition of the OpenDot SummerSchool was organised in June 2020 in a new format, due to COVID-19. It was organised online only and contained four half-day courses that demonstrated how design processes and digital fabrication technologies can innovate the healthcare field by producing effective solutions for real needs. Each course was dedicated to a different design process:

- **Parametric Design** to learn how to quickly adapt objects to the specificity of the user by changing measures and configurations
- **Modeling for surgery** to learn how to realize preoperative study models, for the realization of prostheses and guides to support the operations
- **Custom orthotics** to learn how to design masks, braces, plasters or orthotics that are personalised and comfortable thanks to 3D scanning and 3D printing
- **Training kit for the medical staff** to design kits useful to medical simulation during training practices.

To collect feedback on each of the courses, online questionnaires were sent to participants after the course. In the **Annex**, we will present the detailed results of the evaluation and provide a summary here.

Overall the feedback of participants was extremely positive. We learned that the online format worked well to introduce participants to software (e.g. Fusion 360, 3d slicer tool, Mashmixer, photogrammetry software) and the logic behind and importance of parametrization, as well as 3D modelling in general.

Challenging in our specific context was the different expertise that people brought to these kinds of events, which gathered designers and engineers with already pre-existing skills and knowledge, as well as health professionals who were new to this topic.

Nevertheless for each of the four courses participants said to have gained a lot of specific knowledge especially related to the use of the software and the wider context of health and care that it is applied in; the majority of participants intended to use the new skills in their practical work, and identified specific areas where the knowledge could already be applied. They also expressed their further interest in this topic, developing health & care projects after the course, and searching for collaboration with OpenDot to advance further. From this feedback we see again the great need for and high potential of training related to the digital fabrication of health and care products.

4. Careables platform: Access statistics

In all the *Careables* activities the *Careables* platform was one main instrument to communicate with different target groups, share *Careables* related resources and events and specifically document the created careables, to be shared, and replicated by other users with similar needs.

In this, we look into the details of access statistics to both the *Careables* platform, where we shared all the required information around our approach, and the Welder app, where the tailor-made careables are documented. These statistics help us to understand the interests of participants and the acceptance of the platform by the community. The formative evaluation of the platform was conducted in WP3 and is also documented in Deliverables of WP3. This is also true for the interviews with different healthcare professionals that were conducted as part of the formative evaluation.

Careables platform (www.careables.org)

The *Careables* platform, where we shared information, documents, events etc. related to our approach, was

- visited **65,852 times** since the first of January 2020 and
- attracted the interest of **22,477 visitors**.

The graph on the development of visits (red, Figure 2) and visitors (blue, Figure 3) since the beginning of 2020 shows that numbers are always low during week-ends and higher during week-days.

Figure 2: Visitors on careables.org in 2020

In the last months, we can see an average number of visitors per week-day of around 60. During the first lock-down in spring 2020 numbers were a bit higher, ranging between 80 - 100 visitors per week-day.

Figure 3: Visits on careables.org in 2020

Looking at the number of site visits, we can see an average of 200 to 300 site visits during week-days, but we can also see stronger peaks in May, June, August, September, and November 2020.

Specifically interesting is for us to see which pages are accessed most often.

ID	Title	Link	Visits
1	Home Page	/	22,009
2	About	/about/	4,332
3	Discover Careables	/discover-careables/	2,598
4	Tools	/resources/	1,880
5	Stories	/stories/	1,453
6	Emergency	/emergency/	1,298
7	Seven future careables	/story/seven-future-healthcare-solutions/	1,289
8	News and events	/news-and-events/	1,096
9	Join the Careables Maker Gathering, 25th of June [online]	/event/join-the-careables-maker-gathering-25th-of-june-online/	929
10	Careables Maker Gathering Closing Session: Viral Response Roundtable by Wikifactory	/event/careables-maker-gathering-end-session-viral-response-roundtable-by-wikifactory/	592

Figure 4: Top-10 pages on careables.org

The list of top-10 pages (see Figure 4) shows that visitors are highly interested in the **“About”** page (4,322 visits), which presents the team standing behind *Careables*.

Then visitors use the *Careables* website as

- an entry point to the careables documented in Welder, the **Discover careables-** page (2,598 visits),
- they search for **Tools** related to *Careables* (1,880 visits),
- **Stories** (1,453 visits) and
- **Events** (1,096 visits).
- The **COVID-19** related page generated 1,298 visits.

There was also strong interest in very **specific events**:

- 929 visits of the Maker Gathering event announcement², and
- 592 visits to the Maker Gathering Closing session³

and **specific stories**:

- more than 1200 visits to the story that introduced 7 careables created by people with physical needs and makers together with our WAAG team in Amsterdam⁴

Welder Platform (<https://www.welder.app/careables>)

More detailed insights from access statistics can be gained from the Welder Platform. Welder is the core of *Careables*, it is the place where all the developed careables are documented and shared with interested users.

The *Careables* Welder Platform:

- attracted **7,323 users** since January 2020 (see Figure 5) and
- generated nearly **200,000 page views** in this time (see Figure 6)

Figure 5: Users on the Careables Welder App

Figure 6: Pageviews on the Careables Welder App

² <https://www.careables.org/event/join-the-careables-maker-gathering-25th-of-june-online/>

³ <https://www.careables.org/event/careables-maker-gathering-end-session-viral-response-roundtable-by-wikifactory/>

⁴ <https://www.careables.org/story/seven-future-healthcare-solutions/>

Figure 5 shows the number of users accessing the *Careables* Welder platform in 2020. The highest number of users can be observed between April and June - the time when the maker community was very active in supporting health and care professionals during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic.

90% of our users were new to Welder in 2020. They visited on average 20 pages per session. This is a very high number and can be explained either by the fact that users browsed through several different careables documented on Welder, or they accessed a specific careable several times during a session, which might point to their active interest by accessing the details of each documentation.

Most users came from Italy (15%) and the United States (14%), followed by Germany (7%), Brazil (6%), India (5%) United Kingdom (4%) and the Netherlands (4%).

This distribution (see Fig. 7) shows that we successfully disseminated our approach across the world and have users interested in *Careables* from countries of the global north and south alike.

Country ?	Acquisition		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?
	7,323 % of Total: 100.00% (7,323)	7,228 % of Total: 100.08% (7,222)	9,677 % of Total: 100.00% (9,677)
1. Italy	1,076 (14.81%)	1,072 (14.83%)	1,748 (18.06%)
2. United States	1,023 (14.08%)	1,024 (14.17%)	1,181 (12.20%)
3. Germany	514 (7.07%)	506 (7.00%)	731 (7.55%)
4. Brazil	408 (5.62%)	409 (5.66%)	622 (6.43%)
5. India	362 (4.98%)	362 (5.01%)	402 (4.15%)
6. United Kingdom	297 (4.09%)	296 (4.10%)	322 (3.33%)
7. Netherlands	281 (3.87%)	267 (3.69%)	492 (5.08%)
8. Spain	219 (3.01%)	220 (3.04%)	240 (2.48%)
9. Canada	177 (2.44%)	177 (2.45%)	197 (2.04%)
10. South Africa	153 (2.11%)	153 (2.12%)	170 (1.76%)

Figure 7: Users from different countries

The number of page views (Figure 6) shows an overall high number of 192,225 page views.

Unique page views count for around 20,000. The large difference can be explained by the fact that users accessed a careables page (or elements of it, like the specific documented data) several times during a session.

The most accessed pages on Welder are all related to careables that were created as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic (see Table 2).

Table 2: COVID-19 related careables with highest access numbers

<p>Hands-Free Door opener https://www.welder.app/careables.org/hands-free.door.opener/</p>	<p>971 unique pageviews 30,976 page views</p>	
<p>Face Mask https://www.welder.app/careables.org/my.face.mask/</p>	<p>561 unique page views 25,775 page views</p>	
<p>Air conditioned, ventilated helmet https://www.welder.app/careables.org/my.space.helmet/</p>	<p>287 unique page views 16,613 page views</p>	
<p>WHO recommended hand-rub https://www.welder.app/careables.org/who-recommended.handrub.formulations/</p>	<p>188 unique page views 15,205 page views</p>	

<p>Reusable frame for face masks https://www.welder.app/careables.org/intubation.bboxes.recap/</p>	<p>162 unique page views 9,471 page views</p>	
<p>NanoHack face mask https://www.welder.app/careables.org/nanohack/</p>	<p>157 unique page views 8,537 page views</p>	
<p>Covid-19 protection kit https://www.welder.app/ricardo.freire/covid-19.basic.protection.kit/</p>	<p>185 unique page views 7,364 page views</p>	
<p>Prusa protective face shield https://www.welder.app/ricardo.freire/prusa.protective.face.shield/</p>	<p>242 unique page views 5,703 page views</p>	
<p>Intubation station https://www.welder.app/careables.org/intubation.bboxes.recap/</p>	<p>85 unique page views 3,620 page views</p>	

The most often accessed careables that were not related to Covid-19 are presented in Table 3:

Table 3: Not-COVID-19 related careables with highest access numbers

<p>Made in Shows https://www.welder.app/jon.rushton/made.in.shoes/</p>	<p>32 unique page views 1,511page views</p>	
<p>Nintendo Switch Controller https://www.welder.app/careables.org/nintendo.switch.pro.controller.handicap.mod/</p>	<p>40 unique page views 1,383 page views</p>	
<p>Glifo https://www.welder.app/careables.org/glifo.-writing.tool</p>	<p>44 unique page views 907 page views</p>	

The statistics show the importance of some contributors, e.g. the Brazilian Careables hub in Olinda (presented in Chapter 6) had 791 unique page views (and 15,242 page views) on their careables.

The creation form, which serves to upload new careables to the Welder App, has 140 unique page views.

5. Covid-19 response of makers: Introduction and summary

As can be seen, by actual access statistics the COVID-19 response of makers had an important influence on the project's activities and impact. During the rapid spread of the novel Coronavirus (Covid-19) worldwide, which puts our health systems under unexperienced pressure and brings them close to collapsing in some countries, we are all witnessing the importance of the maker community for a rapid response to the lack of medical hardware supplies. Across the world we see initiatives popping up where maker spaces are called to use their digital fabrication tools to e.g. 3D print valves for life-saving Coronavirus treatments or face shields to offer some protective gear for doctors (Ranney, et al. 2020). As we also see from some of the case descriptions above they have included their COVID-19 response activities.

But not only has the maker community contributed to the rapid production of needed pieces, it also has been showing its responsible innovation capacities by rapidly prototyping, testing, documenting and reproducing new products that are needed in times of this pandemic, such as hands-free 3D-printed door openers to help against the spread of Coronavirus. Medical Hackathons are organised around the globe to design and deploy open source hardware (OSH) medical products (e.g. Coetzee 2020). However, this first aid response of the maker community does not go without friction, especially when dealing with critical medical equipment that needs to adhere to strict quality control and standards and represents a large business field for companies specialised in this area. One of the first instances of such a conflict appearing in international media was the case of a volunteer maker in Italy, who produced 3D-printed valves for life-saving Coronavirus treatments (Peters 2020). The original manufacturing company had refused to release the design files for the valves, forcing the volunteer maker to reverse-engineer the valve. The ethical question that remains to be answered in this case is whether the original manufacturer did not release the original files due to a concern of quality or due to a business-driven motivation. The great concern for quality standards is shared across the maker communities and they rapidly established working groups and testing spaces with doctors and health specialists. Makers are working with medical review teams to validate the utility and safety of new solutions quickly, before entering them into an open source hardware collaboration and hosting platform.

The bottom-up initiatives from maker networks across the globe, including *Careables*, are currently showing us how responsible innovation is happening outside the constraints of profit-driven large industries. We are witnessing critical, socially responsible making these days and professionalisation of the

maker-driven open hardware movement that is comparable to open source software that is running the world nowadays. But, is the maker community putting social interests before business interests? What effects will the open source hardware designs, that are currently being created and shared, have on the future of manufacturing? Will we see new collaborations across established industries and makers emerging? How will this affect society and especially the younger generation? These are just some of the emerging questions that science and technology studies in a joint effort of different disciplines still have to find answers for.

To summarise the experiences made by the *Careables* network we submitted a manuscript to the *Frontiers in Sociology* special edition: *Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19): Socio-Economic Systems in the Post-Pandemic World: Design Thinking, Strategic Planning, Management, and Public Policy*⁵ where we present different cases from our *Careables* network of makers that contributed to the production of personal protective equipment (PPE) and healthcare related products. In Brazil, e.g. four maker spaces (LabCOCO, Casa Criatura, Coletivo 3D, and LabProComum) based in the coastal cities of Olinda and Santos function as hubs to connect patients and carers to the *Careables* maker community. Together with the Secretary of Health of Olinda they decided to address the lack of protective equipment in the region by beginning research into developing materials that could halt the spread of the coronavirus, producing up to 140 face shields per day that were delivered to local hospitals (see the full manuscript in the Annex for more details). The face shields are adaptations of open source product designs shared globally across the maker communities. In Italy, the designs of PPE and medical support equipment were freely shared on a nation-wide platform (<https://techforcare.com/>) in order to be replicated locally. We draw our cases from the experiences made in *Careables*, with the presented cases in this study we reflect on the potential implications for post-pandemic local production of healthcare products. These global experiences are valuable indications of a transformative innovation that can reduce dependencies from international supply chains and mainstream mass production.

The submitted manuscript, which is still under review at the time of writing this deliverable, is in the Appendix.

⁵ <https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/13913/coronavirus-disease-covid-19-socio-economic-systems-in-the-post-pandemic-world-design-thinking-strat>

6. Worldwide careables Hubs

During the three project years careables fostered the formation of careables Hubs, understood as local partners that drive, disseminate and represent the *Careables* approach in their regions and countries. These local *Careable* partners around the world were not only important players when it comes to responding to the COVID-19 pandemic. They were also important players in developing careables for people with specific needs, in disseminating our approach and training a large range of stakeholders in the required skills.

In the following section we introduce the activities and impact of the worldwide careables Hubs and show the richness of the approaches taken and the manifold benefits for the involved target groups. We will start this summary with the careables Hubs in Europe, who were core members of the Consortium, and will then introduce the careables Hubs in Brazil, Ghana and Nepal.

6.1. Careables Hub in Amsterdam / Netherlands

Careables-related activities

During the first 1,5 years, the *Careables* team from WAAG⁶ in the Netherlands actively focused on developing the *Careables*-process (the series of workshops to bring together the network of people with healthcare challenges, healthcare professionals, makers and designers). They hosted a prototyping series three times in total. This method is also included in the toolkit. To engage with people that have an interest in *Careables*, they hosted single open evenings. This provided participants to join for just one evening, instead of six to eight workshops.

Every year, Waag collaborated with Opendot at the International Fab Conference⁷, to gather insights on the work that other Fab Labs have been doing in the field of healthcare. The *Careables* team in Amsterdam also shared their experiences on the *Careables*-process with attendees. In the Amsterdam context, they reached out to other maker groups, such as the sensemakers⁸ (a meet-up group that is focusing on sensors, quantified self etc.).

⁶ <https://waag.org/en/theme/we-care>

⁷ <http://www.fab11.org/>

⁸ <https://www.sensemakersams.org/>

The reproduction sessions in Amsterdam were twofold. In the COVID19-response, Waag replicated and adjusted the door handle and face shields.

Waag introduced the *Careables*-process and several careables to students of the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences. Students could choose one locally designed careables and continue working on this. This was partly reproduction and partly adjusting. Several student groups collaborated with the initiators of the careables.

Furthermore, Waag presented and introduced *Careables* throughout the entire project in a diverse context: in an academic context, and at conferences. But they also organised public evenings where one careable was the center point (Feminity).⁹

In their activities, the *Careables* team in Amsterdam created links to the following organisations:

- Spaarne hospital (Haarlem), NoordWest Ziekenhuisgroep (Alkmaar), Antoni van Leeuwenhoek cancer hospital.
- Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (educational modules presenting cases, and adjustment of careables)
- Tetem (is a platform for presentation and research within a network of creative makers and thinkers); Tetem is adopting the *Careables* method in their locations.
- Contact Amsterdam - creative hub and makerspace, where they hosted two Make Health prototyping series.

Perceived impact and achievements

"In the MakeHealth prototyping process we experienced the value of careables for all participants and how their mindset changed. It was amazing to see the potential, and it's potential for our future healthcare system. It has been a great pleasure and privilege to work with the Made4You partners in the last years, and we hope to keep continuing the collaboration in new settings!" Paulien, Waag Amsterdam

One participant (Debby Marchena) of the 'Make Health prototyping series' makerspace continued her work on developing a lightup white cane (for visually impaired people)¹⁰. She collaborated with several student teams (both at the Amsterdam University of Applied Science, but also different schools). Debby is

⁹ <https://waag.org/en/article/femininity-discussing-speculum>

¹⁰ <https://www.welder.app/debby.marchena/.pimping.my.cane/>

preparing a crowdfunding campaign, to be launched at the end of this year. To collect enough funds to boost the development beyond the prototyping stage, and be able to produce the lightup cane for other visually impaired persons (that don't have the opportunity to build it themselves). Waag will support Debby's campaign with the socials.

The collaboration that was started with several hospitals is still viable. However, due to COVID-19 they haven't been able to implement Make Health further. In the coming months, when the pressure of COVID-19 is decreasing, the *Careables* team will engage with the hospitals to see how implementation could be done. They also believe that the 'word of *Careables*' should be spread by ambassadors. These ambassadors can organise their own *Careables*-related events. Bringing the different stakeholders (healthcare professionals, people with healthcare challenges, makers and designers) together is the cornerstone. This should be done by a network of organisations within the Netherlands. Waag would function as an expert organisation, where ambassadors could go for advice and support. The toolkit provides a solid base for the ambassadors/organisation to start with *Careables*. It takes time for organisations to start these activities, and funding is necessary. Finding the funds is a barrier.

One employee of Waag (Paulien) started her own company - called Studio Junctuur.

Studio Junctuur aims to transform healthcare through design and design processes. Paulien strongly believes that design processes can support the change within the healthcare system that is needed. Applying design processes enables healthcare professionals as well as people with healthcare challenges to change their mindset and perspective. The experience of *Careables* has shown that design processes can do this. Based on these experiences Paulien would like to continue to work on these transitions, and also expand her work to local communities. The company started in July (although Paulien registered the name at the Chamber of Commerce in January).

Barriers and challenges

Finding appropriate funds to execute activities is the main barrier, also for ambassadors to continue and spread the work on *Careables*. The funding for participants to create their prototypes could also be a challenge. The first prototype usually is limited in costs, but to create a fully functional prototype means an increase in costs. Not all participants are able to cover these costs.

A challenge is also to really include healthcare organisations. Engaging with individual healthcare professionals is manageable by proper recruitment. But these professionals can't participate only in their private time. To really implement *Careables*, they also need to be supported by the healthcare organisations. To organise this organisational support takes time and is a long-term ambition (beyond the scope of the project).

Future plans

In the future, the *Careables* team in Amsterdam needs to find additional funds to continue their work with ambassadors and healthcare organisations (when the COVID-19-related care is limited and organisations have time to pick this up). Starting collaborations with patient organisations is also a possibility for the coming years.

They also foresee a focus on training of professionals (instead of hosting events in Waag). Providing 'academy programs' is a strategy to include and train healthcare professionals to change within their organisations.

6.2. Careables Hub in Berlin / Germany

Careables-related activities

In Berlin the *Careables* team from Prototypes¹¹ organized and ran a series of Meet Ups and Open Fablab events around co-creating careables in a user-centered approach.

But their most important activity was the organisation of the Open Health HACKademy in 3 runs with a growing network of partners. Altogether they involved close to 200 participants in three differently organised HACKAdemies and worked on 13 careables for people with specific needs.

¹¹ <https://prototypes.berlin/>

Figure 8: Impressions from the HACKademy in 2020

Together with the project partner be able e.V.¹² and the *Careables* related project MatchMyMaker¹³ the *Careables* team collaborated and partnered locally and across Germany with several Fab Labs and Universities. These organisations provided prototyping facilities (e.g. Wood Workshops, Metal Workshops, Rapid Manufacturing Workshops) and their local networks of makers and students, e.g. the MachBar Potsdam, TU Berlin, HPI and School of Design Thinking, Beuth Hochschule.

The Berlin team also actively exchanged and built bonds with the partners from the *Careables* Consortium and the worldwide GIG members, who were involved in *Careables* activities.

¹² <https://be-able.info/>

¹³ <http://matchmymaker.de>

Perceived impact and achievements

"It's amazing to co-create something meaningful with a very diverse bunch of people." Isabelle, Prototypes Berlin

The impact that the *Careables* team in Berlin generated by organising the three HACKademies with close to 200 people is manifold:

They equipped young people with the skills to co-design health care related products - and these skills range from soft skills, like empathy and collaboration, to more technical skills, like applying the design thinking process and handling digital fabrication tools.

They worked on 13 careables that address very specific and individual needs and range from very individualised careables, like Swen's footbike, to more general careables like an adapter to connect wheelchairs to e-scooters, or a training device for people suffering from lazy eye syndrome. But more importantly, they helped to integrate people with specific needs, make them equal parts of the interdisciplinary teams, being dealt with at eye level and having the important experience of contributing valuable insights to the creation of health & care devices.

Apart from that some of the careables really improved the users' lives, like Swen with his foot bike and Amely, who will provide the co-created dummy of a "belly button" to her medical assistants to allow them to practice the exchange of bellybuttons.

The careables were documented on Welder and are ready to be replicated by other users.

The HACKademies also resulted in important lessons learned on how to set up co-design processes for careables in the on- and offline world and contributed to the creation of material that helps to disseminate and explain our approach more widely.

Barriers and challenges

While organising the three HACKademies the *Careables* partner in Berlin faced the following challenges:

- Reaching the right people with suitable offers
- Finding the right users/Case providers and participants
- Encountering enough funding
- Finding the right expectation management for participants and everyone who donates time and passion
- Keeping motivation up over longer periods of time in a voluntary set up (6 week program of HACKademy or loose set up of Meet Ups with Open Prototype Days)
- Conveying the experience to have a real and sustainable impact to participants
- Making the long term and short term impact visible

Future plans

The future plans of the *Careables* team in Berlin are to:

- Run further Open Health HACKademies (next is planned for Feb/March 2021).
- Run further co-creation programmes on open care projects with more diverse target groups like young adults and children.

6.3. Careables Hub in Milano / Italy

Careables-related activities

The *Careables* team from Opendot¹⁴ in Milano has contributed to the implementation of *Careables* model, mainly with regard to:

- the building of the sharing platform careables.org to collect and publish the technical documentation of solutions to be replicated and shared by heterogeneous users, including healthcare professionals and people with disabilities;
- the creation of a manifesto to share the vision about co-design methodology and a toolkit to facilitate co-design for health and care (see Figure 9);

¹⁴ <http://www.opendotlab.it/>

- the organization of co-creation sessions in Milan collaborating with patient associations, doctors and healthcare companies, using different formats;
- the carrying out of training programmes about co-design methodology and digital fabrication technology addressed both to healthcare professionals and students, makers, designers, such as the Health&Care Summer School;
- the coordination of Italian fab labs and maker communities in the replication of solutions to cope with COVID-19 pandemic;
- the carrying out of a successful kickstarter campaign for Glifo, the writing tool for children with motor impairments and the related work on its parametric design and the online configurator;
- the presentation of the *Careables* approach and its impact in scientific and disseminating events.

Figure 9: Manifesto of Co-design for Health & Care and the toolkit

Figure 10: Funny moment during the 1st Health&Care Summer School

Figure 11: Careables platform - 2nd release

Figure 12: Glifo - user testing :-)

In the *Careables* project, OpenDot has established collaborations with private companies, healthcare organisations, NGOs and patient associations, but also individuals reaching out to them. Hereby a non-exhaustive list:

- Hackability association
- Occupational therapy lab - Unità Spinale, ASST Grande Ospedale Metropolitano Niguarda
- Affidabile, provider of courses for healthcare professionals
- Sanofi-Genzyme - Open innovation area
- Ospedale dei Bambini "Vittore Buzzi"
- Scuola Futuro Lavoro
- Driveworks
- Solidworks
- imaterialize

Then, the partner in Italy has enlarged their network connecting with European projects and interesting organisations working in the open hardware domain, such as:

- DD - Distributed Design project
- Smart - Map project
- UBORA project
- TOM - Tikkun Olam Makers
- TEDH (Tecnologia e design per l'healthcare)
- Field Ready
- Howest university
- FIX-ED
- Wikifactory
- Fab Care

- Fab Foundation

Finally, they had a key role in the Italian coordination of the maker response to the COVID-19 crisis. In particular, they cooperated with:

- *Make in Italy - makeinitaly.org*
It is the Italian association for making and one of the subjects collecting requests for PPE and mapping volunteers on the national territory
- *Tech for Care - Techforcare.com*
It is a national project started by Maker Faire Rome and I-RIM (Italian Institute of Robotics and Intelligent Machines) with the objective of sharing helpful projects “ready to be made” to support the frontline of the COVID-19 emergency, but also to collect needs from healthcare professionals and new ideas from makers and startups.

Perceived impact and achievements

“Amazing! Having the possibility to apply technologies and co-design to improve people’s quality of life is rewarding and empowering. We hope our method will spread and will be understood and adopted by national and international healthcare systems.” Enrico, OpenDot Milano

OpenDot identified four main categories of users that benefit from the *Careables* activities. Detailed numbers are reported in D1.3.

- **People with disabilities:** the main target group, involved in every co-creation, have been the central part of the project
- **Makers and Fablabs:** There was a surprisingly high interest of the maker community to participate in creating solutions that have a real impact on people’s life. This has been clear before the COVID-19 outbreak, but it became even more noticeable during the pandemic. Also, the fablabs met at international events have been keen to understand better how to bring on co-creation with people with disabilities, and in some cases, they were already actively doing so. In this case, there was the possibility to share methods, materials and information.
- **Caregivers and healthcare professionals:** sometimes part of the process, sometimes main co-designers. The *Careables* team noticed a high engagement and interest in learning more. They have also been part of the training activities and workshops, keen to learn better the technologies.
- **Students:** mainly from design courses, but sometimes from therapists and nurses courses. Interested in seeing technologies and design applied to directly impact another human being’s life. Some of the careables documented, have been created by students of “interactive systems,

fablab module” in NABA (Nuova Accademia di Belle Arti) and “Design and Engineering 2” in LABA (Libera Accademia di Belle Arti).

Barriers and challenges

Barriers and challenges in applying the careables approach were:

- Long-term engagement of people - both students and interested people volunteering their time - in co-designing careables
- Difficulties to bring on design iterations and improvements after the initial development
- Fundraising for specific and complex careables development
- Collaboration with healthcare organisations, due to their complex decision-making structure and strict allocation of resources
- Different degree of readiness for healthcare organisations and professionals to innovation
- Possibility to bring on collaboration started during the COVID-19 crisis, outside of an emergency context

Future plans

There are already some *Careables*-related activities for 2021 planned, which are:

- design tables with SIRyoung - società Italiana di neumatologia - that were unfortunately postponed due to COVID-19 outbreak of last March;
- technical workshop on digital fabrication for healthcare addressed mainly to healthcare professionals, supported by EU DD-Distributed Design project;
- closing activities connected to the Kickstarter campaign, as the development and testing of the online configurator for Glifo and its launch.

In general, the focus will be the capacity building of healthcare professionals and organisations so that they can learn to use digital fabrication technologies, co-create solutions that meet their needs in daily practises, be resilient and innovate.

Therefore, the *Careables* team of OpenDot wishes to enlarge their network of stakeholders in the healthcare sector interested in the *Careables* approach, working together to carry out personalized training programmes and co-design workshops involving healthcare workers.

Also, they wish to bring training programmes about digital fabrication into health&care related universities or organisations in the field of higher education.

Moreover, OpenDot is the initiator - together with Waag and FabLab Kamp-Lintfort - of FabCare group composed of fab labs with long-term experience in digital fabrication and health and care and its future activities are to be defined.

6.4. Careables Hub in Kathmandu / Nepal

Careables-related activities

The main activities of Nepal Communitere¹⁵, the *Careables* Hub in Kathmandu, have focused on conducting demo workshops with engineering and design students throughout Nepal to expose them to open source platforms such as careables.org and the principles around Human-Centered Design.

They organised a Humanitarian Design Challenge where four interdisciplinary teams were formed to take an open source health product from the *Careables* platform or other sites and iterate, adapt and refabricate these selected careables after incorporating input from users. This resulted in 4 adapted health-related products that each team produced.

The *Careables* team in Kathmandu has also been working directly with the Hospital & Rehabilitation Center for Disabled Children ([HRDC](#)) to support their health team in 3D designing and printing prosthetics for their patients. HRDC has a 3D printer on site, but are seeking technical support on the digital fabrication from the *Careables* team in Kathmandu.

During the COVID-19 pandemic the team worked with nearby health workers to create low cost mask clasps and hands-free taps to support the general public in practicing safer sanitization practices.

In late 2020 the *Careables* team launched a series of virtual design workshops in collaboration with Field Ready and the Royal Academy of Engineers for diverse participants who want to build digital fabrication skills.

¹⁵ <https://nepal.communitere.org/>

Figure 13, 14, 15: Impressions from Careables activities of Nepal Comunitiere

The *Careables* team in Kathmandu was motivated to become a *Careables* Hub, as they are in the process of launching the first Fab Lab Nepal in collaboration with MIT and the Center for Bits and Atoms and Field Ready. *Careables* seemed like a perfect opportunity to start engaging with the community of makers around the value of open source platforms, design thinking and the social impact/benefits it can bring for Nepal.

As mentioned above, they have collaborated with local engineering colleges and universities such as Kathmandu University and the Engineering College in Pulchowk. They also have a strong partnership with Field Ready and have gained support from the Royal Academy of Engineering (RAEng) and are working with HRDC to support health workers in using 3D printing technology.

Perceived impact and achievements

“Careables has helped us to unlock and showcase the impact and benefits of open source design platforms and digital fabrication can have for Nepal’s health sector.” Bahar, Comunitiere Nepal

The main benefits of the Design Sprint trainings for engineers and design students, as well as the work with HRDC and nearby health workers, is to learn and apply digital fabrication skills from design, iteration to fabrication.

People who got involved with *Careables* were able to see the direct benefit and impact of their products for users who are in the need of health and care.

It was a co-creation process that brought together diverse teams and skills and resulted in products that successfully supported people with specific health needs to better cope with their lives. In the training activities, specific attention was given to gender issues, thus out of the 20 participants, 14 were female.

Barriers and challenges

For Nepal, digital fabrication is still very new and engineering students/makers/designers do not have access to the equipment to practice these essential skills. Thus, the main challenge has been in bringing equipment to makers, designers and students, and creating opportunities to bring this work to life through practical skills. The *Careables* team in Kathmandu is eager to launch the new Fab Lab Nepal that will allow this group to work across diverse mediums to develop change.

It is also challenging to enter the health sector, as not all hospitals are able to procure and engage in “alternative” health product development. HRDC is an institution that already has this equipment and asked for technical support. Therefore the timing was nicely aligned to the *Careables* work.

The strict COVID-19 lockdown made it challenging to continue running more design sprints with teams. *Careables* team members were able to meet with small groups of individual health workers on COVID-19-related health needs, but the penetration was challenging due to FDA requirements and procurement challenges.

Also the *Careables* Exhibit, which was set up in the local hub, experienced less footfall due to the COVID-19 lockdown.

Future plans

Since the new [Fab Lab Nepal](#) will be launched in January 2021, the Communitere Nepal team will use *Careables* as a platform to further engage diverse designers, engineers and makers to use digital fabrication to meet health needs for Nepal.

The Fab Lab Nepal will have a trained and skilled team and will bring credibility to help support hospitals, clinics and health workers. They would benefit from further support to partner directly with clinics and hospitals such as HRDC to produce rapid solutions. The team is also planning to explore co-creating adaptive health products with different communities themselves in the Fab Lab, since the place will be accessible to differently-abled communities with elevators, etc.

Thus, *Careables* can be used as a platform to help Nepali stakeholders (mainly from the health sector and government) to understand and accept the impact that digital fabrication can have, so that they further invest in this skill set and infrastructure for Nepal's development.

6.5. Careables Hub in Kumasi / Ghana

Careables-related activities

The *Careables* team from Kumasi Hive¹⁶ seeks to empower people living with disabilities by removing the barrier of the lack of assistive devices. This, in the long run, would improve the participation of people living with disabilities in their communities; getting an education, having more job and career prospects, and having their voices heard.

Their objectives are to:

- Grow a community in Ghana with the focus of fostering the building and maintenance of assistive technologies locally.
- Increase the capacity of people to build assistive technologies.
- Document the activities that enable other groups of people to replicate them.

Having these objectives in mind the *Careables* team in Kumasi engaged with makers, medical experts and people with specific needs and real and virtual gatherings and also organised a *Careables* moving exhibition.

Figure 16: Careables workshop of Kumasi Hive

¹⁶ <https://kumasihive.com/>

Figure 17: Careables moving exhibition of Kumasi Hive

The Kumasi team was motivated to join the *Careables* team, as it aligns with the goal of Kumasi Hive as an organization: to locally create and maintain innovations by the local community of individuals.

The overall goal of *Careables* is one that is important to be achieved in Ghana and thus they engaged relevant stakeholders to actively help people living with disabilities create and access economic opportunities.

These stakeholders were:

- Family Medicine Directorate/Unit,
- Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital,
- Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (Biomedical Engineering and Rehabilitation and Disability departments),
- Makers Assemble and
- Africa Makers Network.

Perceived impact and achievements

Through the *Careables* activities, 18 students (male - 9, female - 9) have received training in foundational concepts in Product Design, Introduction to CAD with Fusion 360, Parts Design, Basic Electronics, Electronic Circuit Design for Industrial PCB Production, Material Selection in a period of 6 weeks.

Also, the Kumasi *Careables* team has exhibited the white cane designed by the students to the Family Medicine Directorate (KATH) and during the Africa Makerspace Gathering 2020 held virtually. Feedback has been gathered from

these exhibitions and should be incorporated into future iterations of the assistive technology.

Figure 18: Careables trainings organised by Kumasi Hive

Barriers and challenges

The main barrier encountered was the COVID-19 pandemic especially due to the mandatory lockdown that schools were placed in. This prevented the *Careables* Kumasi team from furthering training with the students aiming at the co-creation of other assistive technologies. The situation was salvaged through an online mini project where students had to design an assistive device for people living with arthritis to be able to open and shut a door using its knob.

Future plans

Future plans will focus on:

- Establishing a strong *Careables* community in Kumasi.
- Improving the initial prototypes of the white cane and door knob to more advanced and cost-effective designs.
- Motivating makers in Kumasi to go into assistive Tech innovations through workshops where they can develop their skills in digital fabrication and also participate in innovation challenges to develop cost effective assistive tech.
- Setting up a Creativity and innovation Space for makers where they can meet and build.

In order to execute these plans, the main wish is to get enough funding for setting up a Creativity and Innovation Space for makers, organizing workshops and innovation challenges, improving the prototypes and to support community activities.

6.6. Careables case in Olinda / Brazil

Careables-related activities

The *Careables* partner Casa Criatura¹⁷ in Olinda was the first *Careables* Hub in Brazil.

They have organised and been involved in several physical maker gatherings and events before the COVID-19 pandemic, fostering the consciousness about health and care in the community. While doing this they have developed toolkits and products for healthier food consumption and worked on aromatherapeutic pillows. They also developed and shared a prototype of a low-cost stadiometer.

With the start of the pandemic they got heavily involved in the production of different face shield models for the health sector and the general public; together with medical staff from the local hospital they developed an aerosol-box model that protects doctors when intubating COVID-19 patients.

During the COVID-19 pandemic they continued their participation in virtual maker gatherings, like the **Careables maker gathering Brazil** and the **Emergency Lab – COVID-19**, and in related conferences to disseminate the idea of *Careables*, share knowledge and experiences with other hubs and foster the development of careables.

¹⁷ <https://casacriatura.com/>

Casa Criatura also organised a *Careables* moving exhibition.

Figure 19: Careables promotion material of Casa Criatura

The Casa Criatura team were motivated to join the *Careables* project, as they wished to become part of an international network on health and making, get access to toolkits and methodologies to apply an educational process, share perspectives on health, care and making with others and be funded to work with a vibrant and significant project.

As careables Hub they have created links to the

- Secretary of Health of Olinda
- Grupo de Apoio à Criança com Cancer Recife (Support Group for Children with Cancer - Recife) - <http://www.gac.org.br/>
- SAMU School Hospital - Cabo de Santo Agostinho
- Cadus - cadus.org
- Mozilla Foundation
- Instituto Procomum - <https://procomum.org>

- Glipho & OpenDot - <http://www.toscanotto.com/portfolio/glifo/>
- ScienceCamp (Iraq)

Perceived impact and achievements

"Careables saved many lives. (or, as we heard from many doctors: " You are saving lives")" Ricardo, Casa Criatura in Olinda

Casa Criatura gathered around 100 people in their physical maker gatherings and events before the COVID-19 pandemic. In these gatherings, they not only disseminated the *Careables'* idea of open source health care support, but also developed open source careables.

Their participation in different online panels and conferences, in Brazil and outside, transferred the message of *Careables* to around 1000 viewers. Also the media were successfully involved.

They have been a very active player in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic and delivered more than 7000 face shields:

- 1500 to indigenous communities health authorities;
- 1500 to charity and assistance institutions;
- 4000 to Public and Private hospital professionals in Recife Metropolitan Area and Caruaru city.

They also delivered more than 3000 FuFace Mask adapted with an extra filtering layer;

Around 10 of their open source careables are documented and available to download on the Welder platform.

Barriers and challenges

The experiences in Olinda show that gathering the community - patients, doctors, designers - is not simplistic, as their personal interest fields can diverge significantly. But the pandemic had a positive impact, with all the groups willing to co-create solutions in the short-term.

Another challenge that still needs to be addressed is the significant amount of plastic disposed of in nature by the activity of producing face shields.

Future plans

For the months to come the *Careables* team in Olinda plans to:

- Better organize their bio-fermentation lab production and distribution.
- Create more careables related to natural self-care (aromatherapy, teas, sprouts) production

- Organize the logistics of 100 Glifo donations to a local hospital (personalize each pen, find the most suitable logistics for production and deliver together with OpenDot)
- Keep supporting the secretary of health of Olinda on careables production

What they need for that is:

- Regular meetings with worldwide *Careables* innovation hubs;
- Maintenance of the actual platforms to be shared and to host *Careables* library of toolkits and products;
- Translation of some of the content to Portuguese;
- A strategy for an international fundraising action;

6.7. 6.4. Careables case in Santos / Brazil

Careables-related activities

The Procomum Institute¹⁸ in Santos was the second *Careables* Hub in Brazil and created strong links with Casa Criatura in Olinda. They established strong connections between both labs and related communities in both localities/hubs dedicated to the exchange of knowledge and experiences on technology and health. This collaboration was initiated by a launch event in Olinda and deepened via the **Careables Maker Gathering Brazil**, which happened in four meetings for conversations, deepening, exchanging knowledge and sharing information on the prototypes developed at LAB Procomum and Casa Criatura during 2020 in the *Careables* project. Each laboratory presented two developed prototypes.

The two *Careables* partners also organised a series of three online conversations about the relationship and connection of ancestral knowledge and the advancement of technology in health.

As reaction to the COVID-19 outbreak in Brazil, the Institute in Santos supported the **face shield task force**, a voluntary task force, which distributed face shields to public hospitals, alongside community leaders that were in the forefront of emergency help actions.

¹⁸ <https://www.procomum.org/>

Figure 20: Launch event of the Careables Maker Gathering Brazil

From 15 to 19 June 2020, the *Careables* team in Santos supported the 2nd Edition of the **Emergency Lab – COVID-19**. This virtual lab was an online event, composed of several institutes and people who aimed to foster collaboration and innovation in a virtual space to create solutions to the complex problems facing their communities in the face of the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. It offered a virtual space for strategic development, running five days of remote work, where projects were connected to different resources and knowledge. Through two open calls, one for projects and one for collaborators, the Emergency Lab sought for projects mainly from rural and urban peripherals, connected ideas with a large number of collaborators, to spread these initiatives, help in structuring them so that they can be replicated and also offer mentoring and allowances for proposals.

From 30th November to 11th December 2020, the Procomum Institute in Santos organised a **Careables moving exhibition**. The People exhibition (objects, projects and technologies) is being held at the headquarters of the NGO Arte no Dique, in Santos-SP. The objective is to show, in a playful and interactive way, the prototypes developed during the project: the low-cost medical monitoring monitor, prototyped by Rafael Teixeira (São Paulo-SP); and the making of personal protective equipment for health professionals, carried out by Santos Hacker Clube (Santos-SP). To build the narrative of the development of the prototypes, to present their documentation and operation, the scenographer and art director Daniel Calado, who composes the network of LAB Procomum, built a playful and interactive exhibition, in the format of a game and scenario with recyclable objects.

Figure 21: Invitation to the Careables moving exhibition in Santos

Procomum was motivated to join the *Careables* team in Brazil, as it was attracted by the network character, its central value in open design and replicable technologies; that people are coming before technology and experimentation and documentation are fundamental values. These values are essential for the Procomum Institute, following the mission of promoting cooperation, experimentation and citizen innovation for the construction of solutions to problems of our time.

A series of networks were built or strengthened from the Procomum participation in the *Careables* project, including links with Casa Criatura in Olinda and Silo, a civil society organization dedicated to fostering and publicizing cultural projects in rural areas. The *Careables* team in Santos also worked with a network of civil society organizations in the region, public and private hospitals and the Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP).

Perceived impact and achievements

"The project helped to talk about both health and technology in a more simplified and accessible way, incorporating people other than health and technology professionals in the debate - in our case, essentially people from low-income communities, who are normally seen as beneficiaries and not as knowledge and tech producers." Georgia, Procomum

The *Careables* team in Santos worked with three types of community:

- the community surrounding the Lab, central Santos, which is extremely vulnerable.
- the community of hackers, makers and other creatives in the region.
- the enlarged national and international community of people and organizations working with themes related to health, care and innovation.

All of these communities were involved in *Careables'* actions in different ways, considering, of course, the physical barriers imposed by COVID-19.

Careables supported the development of solutions such as the low-cost multi-parameter monitor, which can be a technology developed not only in a pandemic but also in extreme situations, costing around 20 dollars and made with cardboard from companies like Amazon.

They supported around 1000 health professionals from hospitals in the region.

They supported at least 50 community leaders with protection for the distribution of baskets.

They reached at least 2000 people with their online events, taking the name and the *Careables* project to the most diverse audiences.

Barriers and challenges

First, the COVID-19 pandemic got the *Careables* team in Santos off the ground a little bit, especially at the beginning. Even when they reacted quickly, they lost the possibility of slow and long-term work with the surrounding communities, which includes physical presence, visiting homes, visiting public clinics, and involving people little by little in the discussion about health, territory and technology.

Second, it is worth highlighting how difficult it is to speak and work with health, if you are not a health professional. Health is perceived as something to be afraid of, understanding a notion of health as a synonym for disease and a notion of technology and health as something for experts, and not for “normal” citizens.

Future plans

Procomum is very interested in following the partnership with Casa Criatura and expanding it to other hubs in Brazil and Latin America, maintaining a frequency of maker gatherings for the construction and development of prototypes related to health and technology. They still have a great desire to deepen ties with African and Asian hubs, in addition to Europeans. They would like to be able to restart the 2020 plans and act more strongly in the territory surrounding the Lab, on the topic of preventive health, public health and health as well-being. Lab Procomum works with communities of practice, they have some working groups that got involved with *Careables* and intend to continue

the investigations next year. In addition, it is in their plans to carry out another prototype lab for the coming year, keeping the line of healthcare projects and free technologies as they have done this year through *Careables*.

7. Wider impact of *Careables* on open healthcare movement and SDGs

7.1. Open Healthcare and Open Source Hardware Movement

Summing up these global experiences presented above we can draw some wider conclusions for *Careables* in terms of impact. These wider implications are mostly related to a **global open healthcare movement**, which will in the long run change our healthcare policies. Here we would like to summarise the current developments that we as *Careables* have been actively contributing to and co-shaping.

The COVID-19 pandemic, the failing of local healthcare systems in terms of medical equipment provision, and the immediate reaction from the maker movement has clearly given important signs that makers are creating impact (see our COVID-19 response manuscript in the Annex for more details). Amongst others, our experiences have brought forward local collaborations between makers and healthcare professionals. We see these first experiences and collaborations that were established as something to build upon after the COVID-19 pandemic, when there are more resources again. The COVID-19 crisis allowed proving that the process has validity for the first time on a large scale. However, what we have also learned and would like to stress here is that it is not within the *Careables* philosophy to target large-scale productions. Collaboration between healthcare professionals and makers can be an important step between local needs and mass production.

We have also experienced that more and more maker spaces are embracing the topic of healthcare. The global network of fablabs created a special group of fablabs, called **Fab Care**, which is nowadays dealing with healthcare issues. This global initiative was established to support fablabs, makerspaces and hackerspaces which are working in assistive technologies, in creating personalized solutions for people with physical challenges to improve their quality of life. The group was initiated amongst others, by the *Careables* partner Opendot, who actively contributed to the group with *Careables* activities. Before, open healthcare was seen as a niche, as our products are so individualised - but now the importance has been experienced and recognised.

In our contributions to strengthening and advancing the open healthcare movement we also touched a number of related developments, such as Open

Source Hardware for Medical Devices, Open Design, Open Prototyping and most importantly, the **Open Source Hardware (OSHW) movement**.

The OSHW movement promotes, similar to Open Source Software, an open-source culture movement to physical artifacts of a technology. A common understanding is that information about the hardware is openly shared so that others can re-make or adapt it. The OSHW movement is thus closely related to the maker movement and has gained momentum in the last years. Especially the COVID-19 pandemic contributed to creating further awareness for OSHW as we have seen open designs, such as MIT's open source respirator, being shared widely and being taken up by the press and other mass media. These open source examples are clearly contributing to making the approach more understandable for the general public.

As all the produced, documented and shared careables are great application examples of OSHW the project has come forward with important contributions, from a more technological as well as a legal perspective. In the technical sense, we are contributing to the OSHW standardisation discussion, such as the Open Know How (<https://openknowhow.org>), where *Careables* is a partner.

On the **legal implications** related to OSHW, and especially OSHW for healthcare, *Careables* made a strong contribution in the recent publication in the Journal of Open Hardware¹⁹. The publication has already started to receive recognition from the OSHW community and amongst legal experts. In the final deliverable of work package 6 we also elaborate on related legal developments that may be influential for *Careables* in the future, such as the right to repair.

Overall, we can conclude that in the realm of Open Source Hardware for Healthcare careables experimented and initiated a lot and was perceived and recognised as an influential player by the respective communities. Now, we still need to further work towards changes in the mindsets of our target

7.2. Careables and the SDGs

In addition to the wider implications described above, we have identified 4 SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) that relate to the work of *Careables*, namely,

- 3 Good Health and Wellbeing,
- 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure,
- 10 Reduced Inequalities and
- 12 Responsible Production and Consumption.

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/4302150#.X-HsLeIKjOQ>

Figure 22: Careables contributions to SDGs

The concrete impact indicators for each of these targets cannot be assessed in the frame of this project as this goes beyond the project scope. To give an example, the target 3.8 “Achieve universal health coverage, including financial risk protection, access to quality essential health-care services and access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all” is followed up by two indicators such as Indicator 3.8.1: Coverage of essential health services. This indicator alone is an index reported on a unitless scale of 0 to 100, which is computed as the geometric mean of 14 tracer indicators of health service coverage. The tracer indicators include data such as Hospital beds per capita, relative to a maximum threshold of 18 per 10,000 population. This is just to exemplify that projects such as *Careables* cannot directly contribute to such data capturing as this is done at country level according to the United Nations SDG metadata repository²⁰.

However, what *Careables* has achieved are important stories that can be added to some of the SDGs and individual achievements that exemplify the SDG goals on a small local scale (see figure 22). The replication of the light-up white cane in Nepal, which was originally designed and produced in the Netherlands is such a clear example for contributing to SDG target 10.2 “By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status”. As our final deliverables show there are many such stories of *Careables* being reproduced that allow people with disabilities to be part of society and feel empowered.

²⁰ <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/metadata/>

8. Conclusions

In the three project years, *Careables* has successfully spread the message of co-creating tailor-made, do-it-yourself, open healthcare solutions for people with specific needs.

At the beginning of the project, we have set ourselves 5 objectives that we aimed to reach during the project runtime. We aimed at:

- improving the accessibility of open source products (Objective 1) and allow anyone to replicate formats (Objective 4)
- foster knowledge exchange (Objective 2) and establish collaboration between the communities (Objective 3)
- improve quality of life or services provided (Objective 5)

As could be shown in the previous sections of this document, we addressed all of these objects.

We have reached out to a considerable number of people all around the world in open days, workshops, maker gatherings, conference presentations, etc. (see figure 23) aiming to promote the idea of tailor-made, open source health care products, fostering knowledge exchange across the different stakeholder groups and creating sustainable cooperations between those communities.

Open Days	Participants
59	1,316
Workshops	Participants
34	1,937
Education	Participants
54	3,072
Maker Gatherings	Participants
31	19,279
Presentations	Participants
114	24,780
Exhibitions	Participants
14	84,880
All	Participants
306	135,264

Figure 23: Careables events and number of participants, taken from D1.3

We succeeded to establish *Careables* teams in Europe and abroad, who act as central points of information and co-creation, driving our approach and becoming *Careables* ambassadors within their countries (as has been shown in the case study descriptions of this deliverable).

Overall, the *Careables* approach proved to have great benefits for those involved in the co-creation of open health care solutions. First, we experienced high interest of makers, local manufacturers and designers in creating and making innovative solutions that have a real impact on peoples' lives. Makers and designers, who participated in the *Careables* activities, reported about mutual learning between team members and the development of technical (e.g. digital fabrication) and soft skills (e.g. empathy). They benefited from the teamwork and stressed the great satisfaction of helping others. This high interest was already apparent before the COVID-19 break-out and was even intensified during the pandemic. We can find in all countries, maker communities and fablabs that aim to better understand how to foster and implement co-creation with people with disabilities, actively supporting the health and care of others.

Second, the *Careables* approach brought benefits to those people and patients with specific needs: We learned that the co-creation experience supported a change in mindset of case owners, feeling empowered to take their own needs into their hands, feeling valued by creating health and care devices that make lives easier.

Swen had a dream come true, as now he can drive a bike, individually co-created and adjusted to the specific needs from his spasticity by a team in Berlin during the second HACKademy. This bike is so specifically created for Swen, it will not be replicable for others, but clearly contributed to Swen's quality of life.

Mine wished for a construction that would allow her to get access to a bag, fixed at the back of her wheelchair, without needing the help of others. The construction, which was co-created by a team during the third HACKademy, was highly complex and might not be replicable by many others, as wheelchair dimensions and settings are so different. Mine feels happy with her bag-back solution, having gained an important quality of life back for herself. And she felt highly empowered by the co-creation work in her team, taking responsibility for her needs and being treated on eye level.

Debbie, who is the case owner of the pimped white cane (co-created during the prototyping series of WAAG), is not only satisfied to have her glowing white cane that supports her moving around safely. She will start a crowdfunding campaign to help others with the same need with the costs of developing more white canes. And her Careable has already been replicated by makers in Ghana and Nepal to serve people with sighting difficulties there.

What Debbie is still planning to achieve, namely the crowdfunding campaign, was already successfully reached by the *Careables* team in Italy. They succeeded in gaining 5.000 euros in a kickstarter crowdfunding campaign for the Glifo - the writing aid for children with disabilities. The budget will be used to equip more children suffering from motoric difficulties with the Glifo, which allows them to draw and write independently.

The face shields that were developed and shared on the *Careables* Welder-platform by the Brazilian *Careables* team as a reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic, were reproduced a thousand times and distributed to local health care providers, as well as people who work in local communities. Also, the instructions on how to produce WHO-certified hand disinfectant with local material at hand protected hundreds of people in Mali from the Covid-19 disease.

These examples show the diversity of careables developed in our project, not only about the addressed needs and concerns, but also with regard to their replicability. We see that most of the developed careables are very individual solutions to very individual problems. This was one of our initial objectives that we reached: addressing those specific needs that mass productions in the health and care area cannot address. But in this case, we are mostly producing for a single or a handful of people - so classical economic concepts that are built on scaling and mass production can not work. When we co-create to improve the quality of lives of people with very specific needs, then funding is a huge issue. We calculated around 200 Euro to create the first prototypes of careables and the organisation of a HACKademy requires a budget of 30.000 - 50.000 Euro, depending on the number of people being involved and facilitation needed. All *Careables* Hubs around the world will continue to support this first application scenario of creating for peoples' very specific needs also at the end of the official project, and try to gain funding for it from additional sources (e.g. another HACKademy is already in the planning for spring 2021).

Third, we have started to closely work with health professionals. They showed high engagement and interest in learning more on new fabrication approaches that might support their work with patients. Hospitals and health professionals might be in the right situation to involve participatory co-design processes with patients and maker experts in their daily working activities. First collaborations were already started in this regard, and relations also deepened during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic, when the help of makers was desperately needed to react to shortages in protective equipment. But we also experienced that in times of the pandemic there was no attention, no time, and no resource to get involved in any new innovations that would go beyond dealing with the COVID-19 situation. We will need to wait until the end of the pandemic to start the dialogue with professional healthcare organisations again and look for **more sustainable collaborations that allow experimenting with our approach** and identify areas where the application of individually

manufactured healthcare devices that do not require strict medical certifications can enrich the professionals' daily work. Work in this area is foreseen by all local *Careables* Hubs described above, also after the official end of the project.

Another scenario, where the *Careables* approach and the understanding of co-creation processes with and for people with specific needs might be of high value, is the **iterative development of more and more mature prototypes** of open healthcare solutions. If some of these prototyped *Careables* are able to scale, we might position our approach as an activity that comes before mass production. As an example, one could think of Debbies white cane to become a careable taken up by a large manufacturer and being produced in higher numbers to serve as many people as possible with sight difficulties around the globe.

Careables also showed that the co-creation approach might be even more **important in the Global South** and that *Careables* activities are linked to the SDGs. In many countries of the Global South local manufacturing is a highly important way of serving the needs of the local population - e.g. the production of disinfectants in Mali, not an issue in Europe but something highly needed in poorer countries. We see successful collaborations with hospitals established in Brazil, Ghana, Nepal and *Careables* being an approach that helps to adapt production to local facilities, available material etc.

In the light of these different scenarios of *Careables*, we also see **new job profiles emerging**. If digital fabrication will continue to rise then we will also see the rising need for designers and engineers, who combine digital fabrication and design thinking skills with soft skills like empathy.

After the three years, we conclude that we started an important work in this project and will continue in different parts of the world, supporting different scenarios of fostering the tailor-made, do-it-yourself approach to health and care. We have the commitment of the *Careables* partners to continue with this approach where more details on this can be found in our sustainability plan, presented in Deliverable 5.4.

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ANNEX I – Detailed evaluation results of HACKademy 2020

Motivation:

Motivational drivers were mentioned during the interviews and specifically asked for in the questionnaire. The responses can be summarised as follows.

The main drivers were:

- To do something good; take part in a project that has real impact, that not only generates a concept but a real product with value for someone.
- The fun and excitement of working with new people.
- The interest in building, experimenting with ideas, applying design thinking.
- The many good experiences of people who have already participated in one of the first HACKademies.

Original statements are:

- “Fancy the challenges and working in a team “
- “Do something good and at the same time get to know design thinking better”

Starting the HACKademy:

The questionnaire contained several questions that investigated the participants' start into the HACKademy 2020. The quantitative questions are presented in the following figure:

Figure 1: Feedback concerning the start of the HACKademy 2020

As can be seen the objectives were clear and participants felt comfortable from the very beginning and at ease with the topic. More diverse answers were given with regard to the information provided by case owners, as some teams struggled with the case owners' availability (more information on this issue will follow below).

As answers to an open-ended question, participants stated that the general information about the HACKademy was enough and provided a good entry point. Concrete suggestions to still further optimise this starting information of the HACKademy were:

- One person said that the long e-mails at the beginning with all the required information were very helpful, but what would have helped in addition is a list of all tools and direct links, as much of this information was hidden in the introductory e-mails.
- One person suggested introducing the results from the last HACKademies I and II and also explain which of the careables creating during previous HACKademies were successfully completed and which not.

The kick-off meeting

The initial two-days kick-off meeting of HACKademy 2020 was mentioned by some participants as being [one of the best moments of the HACKademy](#), both in interviews and questionnaires. It helped to familiarise oneself with the topic, to get contact to team members, to create manifold ideas on how to address the case owners' challenges and get feedback from others. The fact that there was so much time dedicated to the bonding of team members was great and it was stated that people, who did not participate during this initial event, never found their way into the teams the same way as those participating in the kick-off meeting. It was perceived as good that the format was so open (participants could choose with whom to work), a fact that was mentioned several times. The online environment worked well to get to know the team and also the case owners' problem; one case owner shared videos about the problem and also showed his struggles life via the videoconferencing tool; Based on these videos the team generated many ideas and this felt great.

Positively mentioned was also the extremely professional organisation of the online kick-off event, which was surprising for some of the participants, as the HACKademy was free of charge. Working with the Miro tool and the videoconference tool was perceived very differently and more motivating than "normal" work. Several participants mentioned the work with Miro and the online environment as being one of the main personal benefits and learning outcomes from the HACKademy.

More critical aspects that can be considered the next time are:

- Several participants felt initially overwhelmed by the number of different tools that were used during the kick-off meeting (BBB, Miro, Slack) and struggled especially with handling Miro. So it would have helped to have a detailed introduction into the tool before the kick-off and team building activities start.
- There was also controversial feedback concerning some activities during the group building process: while the majority appreciated them, a few respondents stated that some of the team building activities were too childish and “pedagogical” and they would have aimed for a more straight-forward approach.
- For some case owners working 6-8 hours with Miro was too long and extremely tiring. It was tiring to understand where people are in Miro and what they need to do. But not only the tool exhausted case owners. Case owners are very much demanded for in the initial phase to introduce their problem to the team. But somebody who is case owner normally has health problems and thus the agenda should ideally foresee time slots during the kick-off meeting, where the participation of the case owner is not required. And organisers need to make it clear to case owners that they are strongly requested in the initial meeting.
- There were very few mentions that having met in real life at the beginning would have helped the whole process. We would have expected more of this kind of feedback but apparently team building, and first requirements elicitation and idea generation works well in the online world.
- One respondent suggested starting the kick-off meeting a bit later and better work longer, as 10H00 was too early.

Bi-weekly reflection sessions

The four bi-weekly feedback sessions received positive feedback from participants. They were an [important part of the HACKademy](#), occasions to strengthen the team feeling and the feeling of being part of a bigger project, where many people are working for the same cause. They supported getting a glimpse into the other interesting projects, and a motivation to get one's own project clearer, when summarising and presenting it to others.

The quality of feedback received during these sessions was perceived differently. Some respondents thought that they received interesting feedback and opinions from the “outside” and the meetings were a source of inspiration. Others stated that the time was too short to really provide and receive useful feedback. It was stressful to quickly grasp the idea of other teams and provide feedback, thus this time of mutual feedback could have been longer.

From an organisational point of view it was mentioned that the optional character of these meetings was good, and also the length was OK, as it would have been difficult to commit more time during weekdays. One person suggested switching between days for these bi-weekly meetings. When someone has a

fixed appointment on Wednesday it was not possible to join, as meetings were always organised Wednesdays.

A few participants thought that the warming-up, relaxation and check-out exercises were too childish. They said that stretching etc. is fine, but there were other exercises where they rather felt ridiculous. One participant suggested offering 15 minutes inputs on design thinking and methods for ideation at the beginning of each group meeting.

Prototyping sprints at Beuth University & Final event

9 weeks after the HACKademy 2020 kick-off meeting, participants were invited to join a prototyping sprint in Berlin. This sprint lasted 5 days, but participants could freely decide, on which of these days they intended to visit the fablab at Beuth University and take occasion of the provided makerspace, fabrication tools and materials. This event was mainly addressing those participants living in or close to Berlin, or being able to travel there. Others were invited to join their team mates, who were onsite, remotely.

For some teams, the meeting at Beuth was the first time that the team members came together and started hands-on prototyping. For some teams this phase followed challenging weeks of looking for and rejecting potential solutions to their problems.

So, the coming together and working together – in many cases on the wheelchairs - **was a very positive experience**. Hence, thinking about potential ideas having the wheelchair at hand was perceived as joyful. There were many ideas and trying them out with the wheelchair at hand made the prototype become more and more concrete. It was the great experience of meeting each other, trying out the prototypes, refining them and working together towards the final prototype.

Also, it was reported that the teams **worked very well together in this final phase**. Having gotten to know each other during the weeks before, everybody could contribute towards the final prototype, also the ones that were participating remotely. In this hybrid situation two teams made positive experiences having at least two members together onsite, who could cooperate, and the others joining remotely, sharing pictures and ideas via Miro, or supporting the work on video and documentation. So also making the video was a good experience for some teams. Also, the final event & presentation of results was important for participants, as it fostered “having a goal in mind”, to present (interim) results. It was also the occasion to see how happy case owners were with the results. As one member said, “It was a very warm-hearted situation when the final prototype was ready.”

Some teams did not make use of the prototyping days. Either they were not far enough with their careable to start prototyping, or the team could not properly organise and coordinate to be there (partly because team work started to stagnate already before the end of the Hackademy). In one team an interviewee said that he had the feeling that the team lost its spark by the end of the Hackademy. Nevertheless, the interviewee quickly created a video for his team, to have a nice completion of the HACKademy also for his team. Several participants perceived the video input from Vlad as very good.

Concrete suggestions for improvement were:

- The time between the kick-off meeting and the first meeting at Beuth University was too long and this was stated by several respondents. And then there was only a very short break between the first meeting at the Beuth University and the closing of the HACKademy. The question is, if the prototyping sprint could not have been organised earlier? There was even the suggestion to start face-to-face meetings and early prototyping already 1-2 weeks after the kick-off meeting.
- Another comment was that organising the sprint on week-days made it difficult for those who had to work and did not live close to Berlin.

Self-directed organisation of team work (tools, best and worst moments)

After the kick-off meeting, the teams started 9 weeks of self-organised teamwork. The following figure (2) shows what respondents answered in the questionnaires with regard to the teamwork:

Figure 2: Teamwork - feedback of participants

The user journey interviews with participants brought insights how teams organised their work and which tools they used:

First of all, all teams worked mostly online together.

The successful teams organised weekly meetings, using a video-conferencing tool such as *Zoom or BBB*. In these meetings team members shared their updates, discussed new ideas and solutions, distributed tasks and planned the next steps; In two teams there were persons summarizing the weekly meetings to keep all team members up-to-date and involved. These weekly meetings were important to drive the participants' engagement. One interviewee mentioned that it was important to decide on that meeting day already at the kick-off meeting.

Problems were reported with BBB when trying to access it via mobile devices. This would need to be clarified in future.

The teams used *Miro* for documentation, to share the case owners requirements, to make sketches of new ideas, and share links to potential solutions. One team observed that Miro was good at sharing ideas, but it was difficult to give things a structure. Thus the team decided to work with *Notion* (a wiki-like tool) as it supported them in structuring the collected information. Miro is a very creative tool and the HACKAdemy world in Miro (called “Brückendeck” or “bridge deck” and shown in Figure 3) that was created by the orga-team received positive feedback (as is also shown in the individual benefits of participants) but it is **not accessible**, a problem observed by case owners specifically that needs to be considered in future. Below a screenshot of the “HACKAdemy bridge deck”, where all teams had their specific room to document, share, use BBB and Slack.

Figure 3: The HACKAdemy “bridge deck” in Miro as central place to collaborate

Slack was rarely used by the teams to share news between them, but rather to communicate with the organisation team. So, this tool has not been accepted very well. As Slack was hardly used, some participants said that it might have been difficult for the mentors and the orga-team to stay in touch with them.

Some teams created groups in *WhatsApp* for the regular exchange between team members. It was perceived as a good instrument for this regular

communication, the only disadvantage was the difficulty to re-find once it was shared in WhatsApp. One team decided to use **Telegram** for regular communication between team members.

Via questionnaires the respondents provided the following feedback concerning the usefulness of Slack, Miro and BBB/Zoom (see figure 4):

Figure 4: Usefulness of digital tools

Two teams met during this time for a face-to-face meeting. In one case this was a dinner, an informal get-together that supported team building and was not a dedicated working session. In the other case this was a visit of a supermarket, to dive into the situation of the case owner and experience his world when shopping in the supermarket using a wheelchair. It was not only an occasion to get an important understanding of the prototype requirements, it also increased empathy of team members and was said to be an important and great moment for participants.

Other **driving aspects** during the self-organised teamwork were:

- The important role of the **case owner**, who was holding the team together and eager to see the Careable being realised. This was motivating for all team members, helping them to never give up even in times of difficulty.
- A new person joining the team with nicely fitting complementary skills, bringing new motivation and drive to the process.
- As said before, prototyping in real-life (not online) with the wheelchair at hand, trying out the theoretical concepts and finding out what worked and what not.

Also, in the questionnaire we asked participants **what worked out especially well** in their teams. The answers to this question are presented in the following word cloud (figure 5) and it shows that prototyping and brainstorming are in the centre of things that worked well.

Figure 5: What worked well in the teams - wordcloud

Best moments or experiences of the HACKademy 2020:

- Working with great people on projects that aim to facilitate the lives of people with certain limitations.
- The combination of different skills and experiences of very different participants.
- The constructive and very friendly collaboration
- The strong sense of community.
- The joy to meet and work together (also in the virtual world)
- The open and very inclusive atmosphere
- The congenial and empathic organisational team, trying to include everybody and having very high social skills; they are awesome people.
- The way how makers treated the case owners – showing empathy and understanding without intervening too much (e.g. they did not question case owners about the illness, which is the normal behaviour of people getting to know them the first time), addressing case owners at eye level.
- The satisfaction of having a result to share – a real outcome of the collaborative activities.

Things that might be improved the next time:

- New people joining the team in the middle of the process, when it was not clear who was responsible for what.
- People leaving the team in the middle of the process
- Case owners who did not really commit to their idea, who did not provide the required information to build the prototypes (e.g. measurements, pictures, videos) etc.
- Having technical problems with the videoconferencing tool or problems to access Miro, thus it was difficult to follow what was happening.
- Some coordination problems between team members, missing communication or delayed answers/feedback from the team
- Getting the team members comfortable in actively writing and sharing in Miro – not only talking about things but also documenting them in Miro.
- The role of mentors was experienced differently. In one team the mentor gave structure to the team activities. He/she was present in team meetings, intervened when the team tended to get lost in discussions and had a look at the time. In another team the mentor was seldom present, he/she left comments with post-its in Miro. In general, the role of mentors was not clear and also how they differed from “normal” participants. Even for mentors themselves it was not clear how far they could or should intervene in case of problems. Thus this needs to be elaborated in more detail if a next HACKademy should take place.

In the questionnaire we also asked participants **what did not work so well** in their teams and the main aspects mentioned are summarised in the following wordcloud (see Figure 6). It was mainly the challenge of finding concrete solutions to the problems, trying to work on prototypes when being restricted to mainly digital tools. Time management and a clear distribution of roles and responsibilities in the team were mentioned as aspects as well:

Figure 6: What did not work so well in the teams - wordcloud

Worst moments reported were:

There was a phase in their process, when the team did not find any solution to the problem. All the initial ideas that the team created and shared on Miro were dismissed as they did not fit with the requirements of the wheelchair. The team would have needed someone with electro technical skills. New team members who joined the team later could not follow the process; suggested ideas that have already been dismissed before. They were not as much involved and motivated as those participating from the very beginning. The team lost time and one of their core team members, who said that he didn't see a solution to the problem, was demotivated and wanted to avoid demotivating others – thus he left. What helped the team in this situation was a meeting in real-life and working with the wheelchair. A new team member with a lot of experience in making joined the team in this moment and was a great support. When they were undecided how to proceed, did not know which future steps to take; either to work on a first prototype until the end of the HACKademy III or to stop the concrete work and go into a broader investigation of requirements, knowing that the time would be too short to realise a prototype then. There was a time when the case owner was less involved. And in this time the team missed the case owner to understand his situation and increase their empathy. They worked based on assumptions and role plays. That is why it was very good for the team when a new input giver joined the team.

Finally, the respondents to the questionnaire provided the following rating of support structures of HACKademy 2020 (see figure 7):

Figure 7: Feedback on support structures

This feedback shows that the support of the organisational team was very positively rated, followed by the design thinking process.

Personal benefits

Learning new things:

- Learning about the documentation process using welder
- Having the design thinking input and trying it out in practical terms
- Having the video input from Vlad and trying it out
- Gaining new knowledge and experiences on the work in trans disciplinary teams
- Needing to get acquainted with Java
- Observing oneself in specific roles, e.g. the role of a team leader.

Experiencing an online collaboration process:

Get an idea and inspiration how such an online event is organised, have the exciting work with Miro and BBB, see how such an online process is implemented and moderated, observe the dynamics in videoconferences.

Creating the careables:

Developing things that are accessible.

Having seen how satisfied and happy the case owner was in the end and having this very warm-hearted meeting with the case owner

Working in teams:

Experiencing the constructive atmosphere, the team work, seeing how different competences complement each other

Having the contact with very nice people

The specific view of a case owners:

Having something desired at hand

Feeling valuable, being able to contribute something of value.

Here a statement from a case owner:

"The whole HACKademy was very positive, the humanity of this event from the very beginning until the end did me good. I grew personally in the HACKademy, learned that I can contribute things, learned that I can have confidence in my own skills. I always thought that I can be creative, but now my creativity has proved to be enriching even in a technical field of work. Other makers accepted my suggestions at eye level. As I have been on sick-leave since a year, it felt very good to work again, to feel valuable and have a task. I am very proud of the outcome. And it felt great to present it to others. It was very exciting but also very tiring. I feel enthused by the Hackadmey (the idea, organisation, format, participants ...)"

Another statement from a case owner:

"If you are always the last link in the chain that you actually always have to take care of, then it is nice to be able to give input! Basically the whole event is incredibly awesome."

In the questionnaire participants provided the following ratings to their experiences/learnings in the HACKAdemy 2020 (see figure 8).

Figure 8: Importance of experiences in the HACKAdemy 2020

How to imagine a HACKademy in future

Finally, we have reflected with participants on how a future HACKademy could look like: It was perceived as exciting and good to have the HACKademy 2020 as an online event mainly, as it allowed some interviewees to participate, who could not have participated otherwise, as they lived in other parts of Germany. Also, for those living close to Berlin it made participation easier, as people didn't need to move around.

The online format worked well especially during the first phase, when participants are getting to know each other and collect the requirements and first ideas for the prototypes.

Also, the rhythm of activities - the balance between structured programme and free working - was perceived as good by all interviewees.

It needs the kick-off meeting to have a starting point, get to know each other and the problem; this meeting can also be intensive. The kick-off meeting is necessary to approach the problem together, especially for people who have never been involved in design thinking processes before. The team building activities during the kick-off event are important, as they support getting people with different ways to work and from different contexts together. They help to reduce all the different views and find a common ground. Thus the kick-off meeting is one of the highlights of the HACKademy and a starting point and baseline of future cooperation. The importance of the kick-off meeting needs to be stressed upfront and ideally guaranteed via upfront training sessions that everybody has the technical setup to join the meeting.

Also the bi-weekly events with all HACKademy members are perceived as important – especially to feel part of something bigger, to keep the community spirit high and drive continuous engagement of participants.

The final prototyping sprints and final presentation were again highlights for many participants and are important parts of the structured programme that should be kept.

But most interviewees suggested making one major change to the format: starting much earlier with the hands-on prototyping, to avoid losing too much time with theoretical concepts that finally do not work out in practical terms. And it is suggested that mentors should be aware of the fact that if prototypes are really complex, early hands-on prototyping is key.

What needs to be clear as well is the specific role of the case owner:

The case owner has an important role in the requirements elicitation. He has to commit to the process even more, if it takes place online. In this case he has to actively share data, pictures, measurements etc. to support other team members in designing and prototyping the careables. Meeting face-to-face facilitates this task, as the case owner only needs to be present while the team can take measures, try out etc. If the case owner can not commit to actively sharing the needed data, alternatives have to be actively searched for. E.g. looking for other people with similar difficulties that support the prototyping phase.

The case owner is also an important driver and motivator for the whole team. It is for him/her that the others spend their time and invest their skills. Thus, the case owner needs to be committed to participate during the whole process. If this is not possible, the team needs someone else who keeps the team together and takes this leading position.

If there are teams with members dispersed over Germany, it makes sense to clarify upfront how the participants can contribute to the whole process from remote locations.

And it is experienced as an advantage when there are at least 1-2 makers close to the case owner's place to make a face-to-face meeting and early prototyping easier. If this is not possible, then the active sharing of detailed data, videos, scribbles, measurements etc. from the case owner becomes even more important. Or the teams look for other sources of those data needed for the prototyping phase. E.g. if they work on a careable for wheelchair drivers, look for someone else who has access to wheelchairs (e.g. a shop etc.).

Concerning a platform like matchmymaker, this feedback suggests that it can serve to accompany the online part of the HACKademy, the formation of teams, introducing challenges, providing others with updates etc. But ideally it would not stand alone, without the structured activities of kick-off, bi-weekly meetings and final sprints. It could also serve to get new specialised people to teams, e.g. if the careables are more complex and different experts are needed to solve different tasks – so having one core group and experts joining if they are needed.

For the future it is also suggested to cooperate with other related events and extend the HACKademy to other regions in Germany. If these cooperations could be formed there could be different locations throughout Germany where teams meet for the prototyping sprints.

ANNEX II –Detailed evaluation results of the OpenDot SummerSchool

Parametric Design

12 participants answered the questionnaire, eight of them were designers, two health professionals, one student and one defined himself as “enthusiast”.

Participants expected from the course:

- to understand the basics of parametric modeling using the software Fusion 360 - so handling the **software** was a key expectation for this course.
- to increase their knowledge on how to contribute to health & care design (from the side of a designer) and how to dialogue with makers (from the side of a health professional)

Asked about their **personal benefits**, participants mentioned that:

- they learned how to use the software Fusion 360 (so this met their expectations),
- they better understood the logic behind parametrization, the importance of parametrics for democratizing designs and the big world behind it.

When we asked participants if they intend to use parametric design in future, all of them agreed. One said that he would apply it to everyday objects, others speak more generally about their design projects, and three participants specifically refer to the health care sector, where they want to apply their newly gained knowledge.

We asked participants, if they are interested in developing Health&Care projects after this course and 10 out of the 12 participants said “yes”, while only 2 said that they were not sure.

Concerning the course itself, participants provided a positive feedback (see Figure 9). The information before the course, the provided tutorial, the lecture and the organization of the course all were rated with a mean of around 4 (on a 5-point likert scale with 1=very unsatisfactory to 5=very satisfactory).

Figure 9: Satisfaction with the "Parametric design"-course

An exemplary statement of one of the participants is:

"Antonio did a great job in explaining the philosophy, usefulness and value behind parametric design, moreover his explanation of workflow was clear and understandable." (male)

Problems arose due to the different backgrounds and knowledge levels of participants. Those participants, who had already some design and modelling experience, would have loved to dive into more advanced topics, while those with no prior knowledge said that it was fast or difficult to follow.

A very concrete suggestion came from one participant:

" I would suggest to skip the basics of the program in the lectures and let students get to learn the basics through tutorials (as given tutorial before the lecture was really clear and I quickly learned the basics). Instead of repeating the basics in the lecture, more advanced methods or other topics could be explained, so the use of timing would be more effective. Everything else I found useful, clear and effective. Antonio has created a pleasant atmosphere and I was delighted to participate in this lesson." (male)

Modelling for surgery

We received feedback from six participants of this course, among them four designers, one IT specialist and one enthusiast (he chose this description).

Expectations were comparable to the first course. They were oriented towards getting new insights into the software, new areas to embrace and new knowledge about the health care sector.

The personal benefits were to:

- get to know the 3d slicer tool
- understand how to develop projects based on human bodies,
- better evaluate collaborations and support, towards problem solving and process and design management

When asked if all students will apply the newly gained knowledge, all but one said yes, one said that he would still need to learn more.

All participants agreed that they were interested in developing health & care projects after the course.

The information before the course, the tutorial, the lecture and organization received mean ratings of around 4 (on a 5-point Likert-scale, from 1=unsatisfactory to 5=very satisfactory) (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Satisfaction with the "Modelling for Surgery"-course

Concrete suggestions were to:

- receive soon the recordings of the lesson
- increase the networking between participants
- using subtitles in videos and translatable text channels.

Custom Orthotics

For the third course we received 10 responses, seven designers, one health care professional, one researcher and one “enthusiast”. Being asked about their expectations, two users said that the course exactly met their expectations, one said that he got more than he would have expected, two referred more concretely to an increased understanding how to project an orthotic tools, one said that he wanted to know more about healthcare and the researcher expected more theoretical knowledge, but said to be very happy with that type of course too.

The personal benefits for participants were to:

- gain new knowledge how to use mashmixer
- be introduced into photogrammetry software
- learn how to work with 3D scanned files.

When asked if all students will apply the newly gained knowledge, three said that they would hope to do so, while the others agreed. All participants agreed that they were interested in developing health & care projects after the course. All participants stated that the course was very clear. The information before the course received a mean rating of 4,4, the tutorial, lecture and organization of the course had mean ratings of around 4 (on a 5-point Likert-scale, from 1=unsatisfactory to 5=very satisfactory) (see Figure 11).

One comment from a user was:

“It is a training experience of the highest level; I do not know what to add” (male)

Figure 11: Satisfaction with the “Custom Orthotics” course

Concrete suggestions were comparable to the ones in the course before, to:

- increase the networking between participants

- use subtitles in videos and translatable text channels.
- give some homework, like doing your own mask for instance

Training kit for the medical staff

Finally, we received six training evaluations for the fourth course: three designers, one student, one health care professional and 1 enthusiast.

Expectations of participants were rather general this time: learning something new about healthcare, learning the basics for further personal implementation.

Asked about their personal benefits participants said that the course increased their skills and competencies, expanded their possibilities, introduced them into the work with 3D modelling. Only one out of the six was not sure if he/she would like to start a project in health & care based on the newly gained knowledge, others wished to try the software explained during the course.

The best rating with a mean of 4,7 was provided for the information before the course, means for the tutorial, lecture and organization were all around 4 (on a 5-point Likert-scale, from 1=unsatisfactory to 5=very satisfactory) (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Satisfaction with the "Training Kit for the medical staff"

Suggestions for improvement related to more practical experiences:

- Develop physical prototypes, maybe providing a list of materials to source for the purpose
- More meetings and exercises at home, implementing a project using the software

Annex III - Evaluation package

The evaluation package aims at providing a selection of evaluation instruments that were used for *Careables* evaluation. With this aim we have mainly prepared instruments that can be used to collect feedback on *Careables* events.

These instruments are either questionnaires or the user journey interviews that were applied with participants after each HACKademy in Berlin.

1. Questionnaire to collect detailed feedback on motivations, benefits, and format of a co-design session:

In the following pages we provide the main building blocks of this questionnaire

Introduction

In the introduction we explain the purpose of the data collection, exemplified with the text of the HACKademy 2020.

*Dear participant,
we are happy and excited that you took part in the HACKademy ☒
This project is a prototype and a great learning journey for us (as it is hopefully for you too), especially doing it mostly digital for the first time during the corona pandemic. We wish to learn from you to become better for the future events and projects we are doing.
We prepared this survey to better understand your motivations to take part in the HACKademy and your project. Also we would like to learn how good collaborations worked and how we can support it.
We guarantee you that we will not publish any personal data that you may reveal, nor hand any personal data over to third parties. When you fill in the questionnaire, we would kindly ask you to fill in all questions honestly – as there are no „right“ or „wrong“ questions. All additional remarks and comments from you are very helpful for us.
Would you help us with answering these questions for us?*

Thanks a lot! Your HACKademy Orga-Team

Starting the event

In the first, block of the questionnaire, we assembled questions about the initial motivation for participation, the usefulness of the even description, clearness of goals etc. Again, an example from the HACKademy 2020, in German and English language:

Was hat dich motiviert an der HACKademy teilzunehmen?

What motivated you to take part in your specific HACKademy project?

Your answer

Ich habe mich von Anfang an sehr wohl gefühlt.

I felt comfortable from the beginning on

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly
disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Folgende Dinge hätte ich noch zum Wohlfühlen gebraucht:

I would have felt more comfortable if, ...

Your answer

Ich habe mich schnell in die Thematik Hilfsmittelentwicklung eingefunden.

I quickly familiarised myself with the topic of the development of assistive technologies.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly
disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Es wurde genügend Information durch die Initiator*innen der Herausforderung zur Verfügung gestellt. (Frage nur für die Maker)

Enough information was provided by the Challenge Initiators (Question only for makers)

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly
disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Folgende Dinge haben mir gefehlt, um gut in die Arbeit einsteigen zu können...

I would have needed the following in order to get a good start for the work: ...

Your answer

Die Zielstellung(en) der HACKademy war(en) klar und verständlich.

The objectives of the HACKademy were clear and comprehensible.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly
disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Ich hatte eine klare Rolle in und eine klare Vorstellung der Rollen der Anderen im Team.

I had a clear role in my team and good understanding of the roles of my teammates.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly
disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Input

In the next questionnaire block, we asked participants what kind of input they would have liked or needed (e.g. in the form of presentations). The example comes from HACKademy 2020 in German and English language as follows:

INPUT

Der Design Thinking Prozess hat mir und dem Team bei der Arbeit geholfen.

The Design Thinking process helped me and the team at work.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly
disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Die Inputs haben mich und mein Team im Arbeitsprozess ausreichend
unterstützt.

The inputs helped me and the team in our working process.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly
disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Folgenden Input hätte ich mir noch gewünscht:

I would have wished for the following input:

Your answer

Möchtest du noch etwas anmerken?

Anything else you want to mention?

Your answer

Support & Mentoring

The next questionnaire block collected feedback on additional support structures, like mentors and the organisational team. The following example comes again from HACKademy 2020:

SUPPORT & MENTORING

Welche Informationen hättest du gerne im Vorfeld von der HACKademy gehabt?

What information would you like to have received in advance from the HACKademy?

Your answer

Ich habe mich vom HACKademy-Orga-Team gut unterstützt gefühlt

I felt well supported by the HACKademy Orga-Team

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Die Unterstützung durch die Mentor*innen war sehr hilfreich.

The support of the Mentors was very helpful.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Für welche Herausforderungen/Probleme hättest du dir von den Mentor*innen gerne mehr Unterstützung gewünscht?

For which challenges would you like more support from the Mentors?

Your answer

Teamwork

The questionnaire block on teamwork, collected feedback how the teamwork can be better facilitated. The following example is from HACKademy 2020:

Teamwork

Wir haben im Team gut miteinander zusammen gearbeitet.

We worked well together as a team.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Wie oft hat das Team pro Woche gearbeitet und wie habt ihr die Zusammenarbeit unter der Woche gestaltet?

How often did the team work during the week? How did you organize the cooperation during the week?

Your answer

Welche Herausforderungen sind dir in der Teamarbeit begegnet und wie seid ihr mit diesen Herausforderungen umgegangen?

What challenges did you face in teamwork and how did you deal with these challenges?

Your answer

Welche Prozessschritte waren besonders herausfordernd im Team?

Which process steps were particularly challenging in the team?

Your answer

Welche Prozessschritte haben besonders gut geklappt im Team?

Which process steps worked particularly well in the team?

Your answer

Personal experiences

Finally we investigated personal experiences and benefits from the participation in one question block, as shown in the following example:

PERSÖNLICHE ERFAHRUNG BEIM EVENT

PERSONAL EXPERIENCE OF THE EVENT

Meine Beteiligung (durch meine Interessenlage, meine Vorbereitungen, konzentrierte Aufmerksamkeit, Kooperation etc.) war intensiv.

My own involvement (e.g. interest, preparation, concentrated attention, cooperation, etc.) in the event was intensive.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Ich habe etwas Wichtiges durch dieses Event erfahren/erreicht.

I have achieved something important through this event.

1 2 3 4 5 6

Stimme nicht zu / strongly disagree

Stimme zu / strongly agree

Was hat dir am besten gefallen?

What did you like best?

Your answer

Möchtest du uns noch irgendwas mitteilen?

Any other comments?

Your answer

Socio-demographic characteristics

The questionnaire ended with a collection of socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, as shown in the following example:

Wie alt bist du?

How old are you?

- under / unter 18
- 18 - 25
- 25 - 30
- 30 - 40
- 40 - 50
- 50 - 60
- 60+

Geschlecht

Gender

- männlich / male
- weiblich / female
- divers

Mein Beruf / Meine Studienrichtung

My profession / My subject of study

Your answer

Welchem/n Bereich(en) ordnest du dich zu? (mehrere Antworten sind möglich)

What is your profile? (several answers possible)

- Initiator*in einer Herausforderung / Initiator of the Challenge
- Maker*in
- Gesundheitspezialist*in / healthcare professional
- Familienmitglied einer Person mit Beeinträchtigung / family member of a Person with impairments
- Interessierte_r / interested citizen
- Aktivist*in oder Politiker*in / policy maker
- Other:

2. User journey interviews:

Complementary to the questionnaire, interviews are a good option to get detailed insights into participants experiences and benefits from participation.

We used the instrument of user journeys interviews. These interviews were conducted online (via Zoom with participants). Interviewee and interviewer shared a timeline of the event visualized in Miro (see Figure 13). During the interview, the interviewee used the timeline to create a mood curve, highlighting times when the engagement in the event was a highly positive and when it was a rather difficult experience. The best and worst moments were discussed together and also personal benefits, formats of different facilitation formats and suggestions for improvement.

Figure 13: Empty user journey map to be filled in during an interview

ANNEX IV – COVID-19 article

1 **Covid-19 response from global makers: the Careables cases of global** 2 **design and local production**

3
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16 **Keywords: COVID-19, maker space, social innovation, Open Source Hardware, DIY**
17 **healthcare**

18 **Abstract**

19 Makerspaces - informal shared spaces that offer access to technologies, resources and a community
20 of peer learners for making – across the globe initiated a rapid response to the lack of medical
21 hardware supplies during the global pandemic outbreak in early 2020 caused by the Corona virus
22 (COVID-19). As our health systems faced unexperienced pressure, being close to collapsing in some
23 countries, and global supply chains failing to react immediately, makers started to prototype, locally
24 produce and globally share designs of Open Source healthcare products, such as face shields and
25 other medical supplies. Local collaboration with hospitals and healthcare professionals were
26 established. These bottom-up initiatives from maker networks across the globe are showing us how
27 responsible innovation is happening outside the constraints of profit-driven large industries. In this
28 qualitative study we present five cases from a global network of makers that contributed to the
29 production of personal protective equipment (PPE) and healthcare-related products. We draw our
30 cases from the experiences made in *Careables*, a mixed community of people and organizations
31 committed to the co-design and making of open, personalized healthcare for everyone. With the
32 presented cases we reflect on the potential implications for post-pandemic local production of
33 healthcare products and analyze them from a social innovation perspective. These global experiences
34 are valuable indications of transformative innovations that can reduce dependencies from
35 international supply chains and mainstream mass production.

36 **1 Introduction**

maker response to COVID-19

37 “Makerspaces are informal shared spaces located in communal, educational and increasingly also
38 commercial settings, which provide their members with access to technologies, resources and most
39 importantly a community of peer learners for making” (Ahmadi et al 2019).

40 During the rapid spread of the novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) worldwide, which puts our health
41 systems under unexperienced pressure and brings them close to collapsing in some countries, we are
42 all witnesses to the importance of the maker community for a rapid response to the lack of medical
43 hardware supplies (Ranney, et al. 2020). Across the world we see initiatives popping up where
44 makerspaces are called to use their digital fabrication tools to, e.g., 3D print valves for life-saving
45 Coronavirus treatments or face shields to offer some protective gear for doctors (Diez & Baeck
46 2020). But not only does the maker community contribute to the rapid production of needed pieces, it
47 also shows its responsible innovation capacities by rapidly prototyping, testing, documenting, and
48 reproducing new products that are needed in times of this pandemic, such as hands-free 3D-printed
49 door openers to help against the spread of Coronavirus. Medical Hackathons are organized around
50 the globe to design and deploy Open Source Hardware (OSH) medical products.

51 However, this first aid response of the maker community does not go without friction, especially
52 when dealing with critical medical equipment that needs to adhere to strict quality control and
53 standards and represents a large business field for companies specialized in this area. One of the first
54 instances of such a conflict appearing in international media was the case of a volunteer maker in
55 Italy, who produced 3D-printed valves for life-saving Coronavirus treatments. The original
56 manufacturing company refused to release the design files for the valves, forcing the volunteer maker
57 to reverse-engineer the valve (Peters 2020). The ethical question that remains to be answered in this
58 case is whether the original manufacturer did not release the original files due to a concern of quality
59 or due to a business-driven motivation. The great concern for quality standards is shared across the
60 maker community and the rapidly established working groups and testing spaces with doctors.
61 Makers are working with medical review teams to validate the utility and safety of new solutions
62 quickly, before entering them into Open Source Hardware collaboration and hosting platforms
63 (Brown 2020).

64 The bottom-up initiatives from maker networks across the globe are currently showing us how
65 responsible innovation is happening outside the constraints of profit-driven large industries. We are
66 witnessing critical, socially responsible making these days and a professionalization of the maker-
67 driven open hardware movement that is comparable to Open Source Software which is running the
68 world nowadays. But is the maker community putting social interests before business interests? What
69 effects will the Open Source hardware designs, that are currently being created and shared, have on
70 the future of manufacturing? Will we see new collaborations across established industries and makers
71 emerging? How will this affect society and especially the younger generation? These are just some of
72 the emerging questions that science and technology studies in a joint effort of different disciplines
73 still have to address.

74 In this paper, we build on the experiences made during the COVID-19 pandemic by a small number
75 of globally distributed makerspaces and fablabs. We aim to provide rich descriptions of the makers’
76 COVID-19 response and reflect on their potential wider societal implications in the future. The main
77 objective of this study is to critically reflect from within the maker community on the crisis response
78 actions taken, showing current challenges and limitations as well as offering a stimulus for further
79 analysis of the transformative character of makerspaces. We have chosen a case study approach as in
80 qualitative research the complexity of each case provides us with an important context for
81 understanding the issue we are studying (Flick 2017).

82 The five selected cases have previously been active in open healthcare practices and have been
83 loosely connected via *Careables*, a project dedicated to personalized open healthcare
84 (www.careables.org). While these maker communities all vary in their COVID-19 response
85 approaches, which we discuss in detailed case description, a focus group discussion revealed a series
86 of commonalities amongst makers when it comes to scaling their activities, which we then related to
87 the theories of social and transformative innovation theories.

88 2 Do-it-yourself (DIY) healthcare, makers and health & care products

89 2.1 Overview

90 Bottom-up digital social innovations are on the rise, including in healthcare. Over recent years we
91 have witnessed a growing number of grassroots solutions in do-it-yourself (DIY) healthcare,
92 including the development of Open Source hardware and DIY practices which may counteract
93 current healthcare supply shortages. Via Open Source approaches communities can collaboratively
94 improve and co-produce new solutions, in consultation with public health authorities (Richerterich
95 2020). Innovators, users of healthcare products, and communities in healthcare are starting to
96 collaborate by using digital technologies to co-create knowledge and solutions for a wide range of
97 needs. These solutions range from Open Source hand prosthetics, 3D printed writing tools to support
98 kids with physical limitations, to add-ons for wheelchairs, and everything in between. If we look into
99 the medical field, we see similar tendencies towards experimentation and creation of alternative
100 solutions beyond the standardized practices, e.g., in the fields of biohacking, patient experimentation,
101 and Open Source hardware for medical devices.

102 These community-led or civic innovations are responses to societal issues that cannot be met by our
103 healthcare systems nor by industry. Criado, Rodriguez-Giralt & Mencaroni (2016) even position
104 open design and participatory prototyping strategies in a more political context and stress the activist
105 character when applied by the independent living movement in Spain. They relate the experiences of
106 open prototyping with and by disabled people to the critical making notion defined by Ratto (2011),
107 which stressed the learning aspects and the societal relevance of DIY activities in maker
108 communities.

109 Closely related to these critical making properties is *Careables*, an initiative that is rooted in the context
110 of personalized open healthcare development. It is a mixed community of people and organizations
111 committed to the co-design and making of open, personalized healthcare for everyone driven by a set
112 of underlying principles for responsible making. It started 2018 as a European funded innovation action
113 under the Horizon 2020 program and has since grown to a worldwide community, mostly via a global
114 network of social and technological innovators called Global Innovation Gathering (GIG). The
115 *Careables* platform¹ and its documentation repository on Welder-app² currently registers over 180
116 open designs for open healthcare solutions, next to other resources, such as legal and ethical guidelines
117 or training resources. *Careables* encourages care receivers, healthcare professionals, and makers to
118 join forces and to co-create tailor-made solutions designed for supporting and better suiting the care
119 receivers' needs.

120 Further, the global network of fablabs recently launched Fab Care as a global initiative to support
121 fablabs, makerspaces and hackerspaces which are working in assistive technologies, in creating
122 personalized solutions for people with physical challenges to improve their quality of life.

123 Beyond the civic-innovation character, we also see more and more established healthcare institutions,
124 such as hospitals, therapeutic and care centers, starting to work with digital fabrication tools. In some
125 hospitals, makerspaces are already part of their infrastructure (Marshall & McGrew, 2017). While
126 these initiatives are less driven by activism or socially driven innovation needs, they equally
127 recognize the values of local on-demand production of spare parts in healthcare equipment,
128 therapeutic devices, creativity, and innovative prototyping. In these health makerspaces medical staff
129 find access to tools, materials, and the required knowledge to test new ideas and build prototypes.
130 With the experiences of the momentary personal protective equipment (PPE) and other medical
131 device shortage during the COVID-19 crisis on the one hand and digital fabrication tools and skills
132 on the rise on the other, we may experience a growing penetration of a demand for local production
133 in healthcare.

134 These developments obviously bring legal and ethical issues to the table such as do-it-yourself
135 solutions that may not always comply with medical standards and regulations. Problems may range,
136 for example, from intellectual property law (e.g., see the above-mentioned case of the 3-D printed
137 valve) to safety and specific laws for medical devices and PPE. Part of these problems arises, as in
138 most cases product laws are aimed at large organizations rather than small entities. Makerspaces and
139 these new forms of collaboration blur the classic hierarchical dichotomy between producers and
140 consumers (Daly 2016; Kamenjasevic & Biasin, 2018) and result in greater problems in ensuring the
141 legal compliance of the co-designed and co-created products.

142 2.2 Maker's COVID-19 response initiatives

143 In early 2020, when the COVID-19 pandemic had completely turned into the globally dominating
144 health concern, bringing the health systems in many countries to their absolute limits, the reaction of
145 the maker movement was instantaneous. Maker communities around the globe have been very active
146 during the first wave of the COVID-19 crisis by responding to the shortage of PPE and other medical
147 and healthcare-related products. One of the larger civic response communities is the Open Source
148 Medical Supplies (OSMS)³. Initiated by Gui Cavalcanti, the founder and CEO of a robotics
149 company, OSMS launched in March 2020 as a Facebook group, and rapidly brought together a
150 global network of over 70,000 makers, fabricators, community organizers, and medical professionals
151 in 55 countries collaborating on the unprecedented medical supply challenges caused by the COVID-
152 19 pandemic. In their global impact dashboard, the network currently indicates that over 16 Million
153 supplies have been delivered by the global community, with face shields being by far the most
154 frequently produced device.

155 The variety of PPE and medical supplies that have been produced in these collective networks are
156 said to include around 50 different products, ranging from door openers, and ear savers to intubation
157 boxes. These PPE serve as a means to reduce the spread of the virus following the available evidence
158 that the virus is transmitted via air droplets when in close contact with infected persons and not air-
159 borne. Therefore by providing equipment that supports frequent and effective handwashing or acts as
160 disinfectants, helps preventing contact with droplets or helps avoiding contact with contaminated
161 surfaces like door handles, an effective preventive measure is being taken especially in healthcare

162 and community settings. The knowledge and research done by the OSMS global network have been
163 documented and shared in case studies, community stories, a project library that gives access to many
164 open designs, a map to find local response groups, and the Open Source Medical Supply Guide
165 (OSMS 2020). Also, the *Careables* community shifted its focus of activities from supporting DIY
166 healthcare for people with disabilities to collecting, documenting and sharing information and Open
167 Source solutions to fight COVID-19. The *Careables* COVID-19 collection currently includes around
168 50 Open Source hardware projects, ranging from different versions of face masks and shields to
169 intubation boxes and door openers. In addition, background information and legal guidance on the
170 responsible production and use of DIY products are shared with the maker community worldwide.

171 According to a survey done by the Fabfoundation, a global network of fablabs, more than half of the
172 products made by fablabs as a reaction to the COVID-19 crisis were locally approved or medically
173 reviewed by an agency or organization, such as hospitals, healthcare professionals or national
174 healthcare institutions (Fabfoundation, 2020). The same report concludes that with this COVID-19
175 response from the fablabs and makerspaces we are witnessing a locally sourced, globally distributed
176 manufacturing process that reacts to local needs in a much more flexible way than large
177 manufacturing supply chains, and this process “could continue to fill an immensely important role in
178 the months (and years) to come” (Fabfoundation, 2020).

179 Not only has the failure of global manufacturing supply chains accelerated the makers’ response;
180 another important factor triggering the community action has been the financially underserved and
181 fragile healthcare systems in many countries. In the UK an analysis of the maker response to
182 COVID-19 pandemic by Richterich (2020) clearly establishes a link between the national austerity
183 politics and the strained healthcare system. When relating the makers’ DIY production of healthcare
184 equipment to the critical making theory of Ratto (2011) there is also a political dimension coming
185 into play, as volunteers in makerspaces reacted to a governmental failure in healthcare supplies
186 (Richterich, 2020).

187 Overall, the maker COVID-19 response initiatives strongly relied on the sharing of open designs and
188 the values assigned to critical making, such as openness, collaboration, and co-production. When a
189 certain material was not locally available alternatives were explored, either by modifying the design,
190 adapting material that was already available or hacking different parts of the design (Fabfoundation,
191 2020). Richterich (2020) stresses this synergy of Open Source design, use, adjustment, and hardware
192 production as a core characteristic of the maker communities’ COVID-19 response.

193 **3 Social and transformative innovation theory and societal implications of DIY open** 194 **healthcare**

195 The value for civic, social, and transformative innovation that we have seen in the makers’ DIY
196 production of medical and healthcare devices during the pandemic crisis has not been fully
197 recognized just now. Since the rapid emerging of local makerspaces, hackerspaces, fablabs and the
198 calling out of a global maker movement (Dougherty 2012) experts have assigned this new culture of
199 local manufacturing certain social transformation power (Diez 2012, Smith 2017, Millard et al 2018,
200 Bosse et al., 2019, Unterfrauner et al., 2020). The technological innovations advancing the
201 manufacturing capacities of digital fabrication tools have offered a wide range of possibilities for
202 social and community action. As Ruiz et al. (2019) exemplify with the three-dimensional additive
203 printers, that are nowadays accessible on the home market, technological innovations can lead to
204 strong social, environmental, economic, and political implications. The authors argue to regard social
205 and technological innovations not as separate phenomena, but rather to consider innovations in their
206 social, technical, economic, educational, and political realm (Ruiz et al. 2019). The examples of DIY

207 open healthcare production that we have discussed above need to be analyzed in such a multilayered
208 perspective as well.

209 Smith (2017), who studies makerspaces as sites for democratizing innovation activity, assigns them
210 social innovation potential. He describes them as *socially transformative, educationally useful and*
211 *entrepreneurially promising*. They offer capabilities for participation, deliberation and community
212 development, which constitute their transformational and democratic potential. At the same time
213 makerspaces also reproduce dominant values of society and the global economy, e.g., when they
214 follow an open innovation agenda that tries to leverage the makers' creativity for global
215 manufacturing and following prevailing economic growth business models. Thus, we are witnessing
216 contradictory developments of makerspaces, where we have open spaces aiming for democratic
217 transformations next to spaces that adhere to traditional market-driven models (Unterfrauner et al.
218 2020).

219 From a critical making perspective, this path of entering the business-as-usual chain is not the one to
220 follow, and many makers striking a social transformative or democratic path have started a search for
221 more participatory models of production generally, and for the healthcare sector specifically. DIY
222 manufacturing processes based on Open Source design may be social innovations that respond to
223 certain social needs, but they also require new collaborative and financial models. Ratto's (2011)
224 critical making values, such as the societal relevance of making and the potential for learning and
225 gaining critical knowledge during this process of material work, indicate the social and transformative
226 innovation potential of DIY open healthcare production in maker communities.

227 As explained by social innovation theory, social innovations tackle social needs and respond to
228 societal challenges (Holtgrewe & Millard 2018). According to BEPA's (2010) societal levels model
229 of social innovation, there are three interconnected levels, namely the social needs (micro level), the
230 societal challenges (meso level), and the systemic change (macro level) (see Fig.1). At the micro
231 level, social innovations are responding to local social demands, tackling specific problems on the
232 ground that are not met by the market or public institutions. They respond in a bottom-up approach to
233 the needs of particular groups, often including the beneficiaries themselves, such as vulnerable
234 people. At the meso level, we see social innovations that are tackling societal challenges at large
235 social scale or across whole sectors by combining social, economic, environmental, and cultural
236 factors. It usually requires new forms of relations between actors, including adequate organizations,
237 networks, and modes of collaboration for producing real and desired outcomes. At the macro level,
238 social innovations generate system change. This can only happen when fundamental transformations
239 in society are taking place, including a reform of underlying structures, changes in the relationships
240 and powers in society. It often goes along with organizational and institution change, reforms of
241 public policies, new governance arrangements and a changing mindset and cultures, allowing for
242 more participation and empowerment. While this distinction of social innovations at the three levels
243 is helpful for analysis it is also simplistic in a way, implying a somewhat linear view of society and
244 possibly ignoring complex and unintended consequences (Holtgrewe & Millard 2018). For the
245 purpose of this work, it proves to be a useful instrument for discussing results of the makers'
246 experiences.

247 The DIY open healthcare activities of projects such as *Careables* are located at the social demand
248 level, tackling specific problems of people, often from vulnerable groups, that are not addressed
249 appropriately by the market or institutions. The COVID-19 PPE production started at a micro level,
250 but with the enormous impact that the epidemic has on our social, political and economic systems, it
251 also gets attention as a more societal challenge on a meso level. The third level, the systemic change
252 or transformation level, requires fundamental changes in institutions, governance and policies. While

253 in this analysis we will mostly stay at the micro level with the described cases, we want to explore
254 how the actions and networks around the COVID-19 response of the maker movement may influence
255 at meso and macro level, contributing to transformations in healthcare in the future.

256 **4 Methodology**

257 As the overall methodology, a qualitative case study approach was chosen since it represents a
258 versatile form of qualitative inquiry that is suitable for a comprehensive and in-depth investigation of
259 complex issues and unclear boundaries (Harrison et al 2017). Representatives of makerspaces from
260 the *Careables* project and the GIG (Global Innovation Gathering) network volunteered to participate
261 in this case study. They are listed as co-authors and are referred to in the following text as ‘case
262 representatives’, sharing their insights and experiences through an interactive dialogue, guided by a
263 self-reflection exercise and an online focus group discussion.

264 **4.1 Involved case representatives & researchers**

265 For the purpose of this study five makerspaces that have been very active during the COVID-19
266 crisis in very different contexts were invited to contribute to this research.
267 Three of these five are members of the GIG network⁴. It is a global network of social and
268 technological innovators that aims to foster the sharing of knowledge and experience amongst
269 members. Two makerspaces are partners of the *Careables* project consortium. In the following list
270 we introduce the representatives of the makerspaces who contributed to this article.

- 271 · Brazil: Ricardo Ruiz Freire (Member of the GIG Supervisory Board)
- 272 · Cameroon: Nadine Mowoh (Member of the GIG network)
- 273 · Iraq: Nawres Arif (Member of the GIG Supervisory Board)
- 274 · Italy: Enrico Bassi (Director of the makerspace OpenDot⁵)
- 275 · The Netherlands: Paulien Melis (Programme Developer of the makerspace WAAG⁶)

276 In addition to the above-mentioned case representatives four researchers from the *Careables* research
277 team participated in this research. Three of them are female academics at the Center for Social
278 Innovation in Austria, bringing in interdisciplinary perspectives, with an academic background
279 spanning the disciplines of psychology, sociology, pedagogy, and economy. One researcher is a female
280 legal expert working for the KU Leuven Centre for IT & IP Law in Belgium. This diversity in
281 backgrounds was important to understand the complexity of the cases and to improve the integration
282 of diverse perspectives through a series of discussions and reflections. The three researchers from the
283 Centre of Social Innovation were also the ones who designed this qualitative study and took the lead
284 in analyzing the result.

285 In general, the overall culture of this research study was collaborative and cooperative, since no
286 single researcher imposed their interpretation, and the results were additionally discussed with all
287 contributors of the paper.

288 **4.2 Research Design**

289 Two data collection instruments were prepared to learn about and analyze the COVID-19 activities in
290 the five cases: a self-reflection exercise and an online focus group discussion (Fig. 2).

291 *Self-reflection*

292 For the collection of the data, the research team prepared a self-reflection exercise, which guided the
293 case representatives in their self-reflection process. The self-reflection exercise was based on the
294 following questions, which participants answered in relation to their the COVID-19 response
295 activities of their makerspaces:

296 · *Case description:* Please describe what were/are your main activities of COVID-19 response.
297 What motivated you to become active as COVID-19 responder? What
298 partnerships/networks/collaborations have you established or are you making use of? How do/did
299 you finance the production of PPE? Where do/did you get the designs from?

300 · *Perceived impact and achievements:* Please describe the perceived impact that you achieved
301 so far with your activities and what has been the public/political perception of your activities. Has
302 there been any public/political recognition of your contribution? You may also report on the
303 impact achieved by other makers in your community.

304 · *Barriers and challenges:* Please reflect on the barriers and challenges that you encounter
305 during your COVID-19 activities.

306 · *Future implications:* Please reflect on the future potential implications that you see from
307 your experiences with regards to post-pandemic local production of healthcare products.

308 The self-reflection reports, which were filled in by the case representatives during a 3-weeks period
309 in October 2020, were analyzed by the research team in a first round and provided the ground for the
310 structure of the online focus group discussion.

311 *Online focus group*

312 The online focus group was organized on 3rd November 2020 via the videoconferencing platform
313 ZOOM and lasted 75 minutes. Representatives from the cases in Brazil, Cameroon, and Italy, as well
314 as the four researchers introduced above, took part and aimed at elaborating a deeper understanding of
315 the described cases and future scaling options.

316 The starting point of the focus group was a short presentation by the researchers of the three
317 dimensions of social innovation also shared on a Google Jamboard-board and presented in Chapter 3
318 of this article. After this introduction, the case representatives were invited to place their COVID-19
319 response initiatives on the respective dimension of social innovation (micro - meso - macro) and
320 explain their decision. In the next step, a second dimension was introduced, the scale and interaction
321 dimension, as an indicator for connectedness (Fig. 3). This dimension on the vertical axis refers on
322 the one end to a situational awareness, where single actors tend to work relatively isolated,
323 unconnected, and focus on the local area working on very local issues. On the other end of the axis,
324 we speak about distributed awareness, referring to very strongly networked, interconnected makes,
325 who work collaboratively over large areas, or even globally. This matrix of scale and social
326 innovation dimension has been applied in previous studies and has provided valuable insights into the
327 characteristics of maker initiatives (e.g., Unterfrauner et al. 2020).

328 The case representatives placed again their COVID-19 response initiatives on the respective x- and y-
329 axes and discussed their positioning with the group. After this introduction the core discussion
330 focused on two questions:

331 · Do case representatives wish that their COVID-19 activities in the different countries scale from
332 micro, to meso, to macro level?

333 · If not, why not? If yes, under which conditions?

334 One of the leading researchers facilitated the discussion, while the second one summarized the main
335 aspects of the discussion on the Jamboard to visualize the key points discussed. The third researcher
336 took additional notes. The discussion was moderated to make participants reflect on their cases and to
337 gain themselves new insights into their specific situation. In qualitative research the researcher is not
338 necessarily the invisible neutral, but may also contribute to a moral discourse and spark
339 transformative processes (Flick 2018). The online focus group was also audio recorded based on the
340 informed consent given by participants, as a basis for the later analysis.

341 **4.3 Analysis and presentation of data**

342 The analysis of the case studies is based on the self-reflection reports of the case representatives and
343 the summary of the online focus group discussion. Qualitative content analysis according to Mayring
344 (2014) was selected as a suitable approach for this explorative study. It comprises a holistic and
345 subjective procedure that is used to interpret and categorize qualitative data. This analytical process
346 makes sense of the data, it describes and highlights important findings and allows to draw clear links
347 between the research objectives and the summary findings. The conventional approach to content
348 analysis (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005) was used here, where researchers avoid using pre-conceived
349 categories, allowing the categories to emerge from the data.

350 The research material was analyzed through two iterative phases, from 29th of October 2020 to 11th of
351 November 2020 by the three female researchers from the Centre for Social Innovation, who also
352 figure as the first authors of this manuscript. Data were analysed both inductively and deductively in
353 these two phases. Specifically, two forms of data analysis triangulation were carried out by the
354 researchers to ensure a rigorous and robust approach (Leech, & Onwuegbuzie, 2007). First, the self-
355 reflection reports were coded individually by each researcher independently and provided insights
356 about the research material that were shared and discussed. Preliminary codes were then agreed and
357 grouped into sub-codes. The findings from this first coding experience also served as a basis for the
358 focus group discussion, where they were critically reflected with the case representatives. In the
359 second phase of the analysis the original codes were applied to the summary text of the focus groups,
360 first individually by each researcher and then discussed jointly. At the end of this process the
361 following codes, sub codes and a final grouping of the codes was agreed (Table 1).

362 We are aware that this study is exploratory in nature and is giving a rich qualitative view on the
363 reported cases, but is limited in its scope. This is the very nature of qualitative research. Engaging the
364 case representatives in a reflective focus group discussion and being part of the authoring team might
365 shed some doubt on the validity of this research. However, we believe that by doing so we have
366 guaranteed the authenticity of the experiences and our findings are internally coherent. In particular
367 the focus group discussion has helped to reflect on the constructs emerging from the first analytical
368 phase and has allowed the three main researchers to capture data “from the inside” and gain a deeper
369 understanding of the phenomena under discussion (Miles & Huberman 1994). This transdisciplinary
370 approach was important for a meaningful knowledge co-production as described by Thompson et al.
371 (2017). The integrative and participatory processes during the self-reflection reporting and the focus
372 group discussion opened the complex context of the maker movement for the main researchers. The
373 collaboration of the actors involved in this study, who transcend disciplinary and academic
374 boundaries, has been growing over the years and accumulates in this study. We believe that a certain

375 level of mutual trust amongst all co-researchers is important for the transdisciplinary co-production
376 (Thompson et al. 2017), leading to socially robust knowledge in the sense of Nowotny et al. (2001).

377 The following case descriptions represent summaries of the self-reflection reports while chapter 6
378 presents the results from the online focus group.

379 **5 Case Descriptions**

380 The following five cases of maker responses to COVID-19 cover different perspectives and contexts.
381 Some focus on their lab's activities, some relate more on the national activities all together, and
382 overall, they give a good representation of the diversity of actions encountered in makerspaces across
383 the globe.

384 **5.1 The Brazilian Case (LabCOCO, Casa Criatura, Coletivo 3D and LabProComum;** 385 **Olinda)**

386 In Brazil, before the outbreak of the pandemic, four maker-oriented organizations had established
387 collaborations with the *Careables* project and started to function as local hubs which connect local
388 communities of persons with (physical) healthcare needs, care givers, and public healthcare
389 professionals with the community of makers and medical herbalists. With the outbreak of COVID-
390 19, the activities of these local hubs, called *Careables Olinda*, completely shifted to producing PPE
391 and other medical supplies in order to fight the pandemic. So far, they have produced around 7.000
392 face shield units out of which they donated around 5.000 pieces to different initiatives, to hospitals
393 and health authorities in the Recife metropolitan area, cities in the countryside, and indigenous and
394 Afro-Brazilian communities. The remaining products were offered via an e-Shop that was
395 specifically set up for that purpose. The Brazilian fablabs partly relied on shared Open Source
396 designs of face shields and adapted them to the local context. Besides, together with healthcare
397 professionals, they developed an open-source model of an aerosol box integrated into local
398 necessities to use at Intensive Care Units (ICU) and released it online. The aerosol box is used in the
399 process of intubation and extubation of patients, to avoid the contact of aerosol sprays of patients
400 with doctors. The product was validated with doctors from two different hospitals in the Metropolitan
401 Region of Recife, who have experience in orotracheal intubation. In addition, a community including
402 professors, medical students and designers from Casa Criatura was established to develop the product
403 further and is, at the time of writing this manuscript, seeking certification and registration of a free
404 patent, with the final aim of bringing the aerosol box to a global market.

405 Partnerships and networks, local and global, played a crucial role in this case. Since the beginning of
406 its activities, *Careables Olinda* had a dialogue with the Secretary of Health of Olinda, who realized
407 the importance of the maker community in the local production of PPE to keep up the city's health
408 system. Later, collaboration with healthcare professionals and hospitals started as ICU professionals
409 approached the makers with a request for a better version of an aerosol box and jointly they defined
410 the specifications. The relationship with the health sector has allowed *Careables Olinda* to review its
411 area of activity and has expanded the scope of its inventiveness while at the same time it increased
412 local awareness and knowledge about open-source, digital manufacturing and healthcare across the
413 involved stakeholders, e.g., physicists, designers, healthcare professionals, makers. The local maker
414 hubs also felt like being part of a bigger initiative, not only for the producers of PPE. Their
415 communication campaign was a small part of a big operation by different sectors in the cities to
416 suppress the virus and the cooperation with the Secretary of Health has already split over to other
417 activities of open innovation, besides COVID-19.

418 While the activities clearly showed valuable impact in reducing the curve of COVID-19 infections in
419 the regions (contrary to the figures at national level) and in promoting the social value of open
420 innovation, the actors clearly recognize the negative impact of their actions. The enormous amount of
421 plastic being produced, the considerable degree of pollution and carbon emissions related to the
422 makers' activities, coupled with the environmental problems of the local communities triggered a
423 commitment for more sustainable practices in the future. Some of those have already started to
424 emerge, such as the work with recycled plastic or the creation of a bio-fermentation lab to address the
425 food scarcity in some local communities.

426 **5.2 The Cameroonian Case (Mboalab, Mbankomo)**

427 Mboalab is a community biology lab in the central region Yaounde in Cameroon, comprising
428 molecular biologists, biochemists, public communications specialists, microbiologists, and electro-
429 mechanic technicians, who act as educators in the local community to empower the population with
430 the skills to solve their health and environmental problems. During the COVID-19 pandemic
431 outbreak, the lab tried to attack some of the local bottlenecks related to the sanitary situation. The
432 information department at Mboalab accessed the latest information and recommendations from the
433 World Health Organization (WHO), the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), and the Centers for
434 Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), looking for simple formulae for making hand sanitizers and
435 instructions for face masks designs. With their strategy to target the most vulnerable groups and
436 communities (healthcare workers and the local population) of the suburban community of
437 Mbankomo, where the lab is located, they started their educational work. The lab team was able to
438 prepare alcohol-based hand sanitizers that met the FDA recommendation with locally available
439 components and started demonstrating simple formulae for producing hand sanitizers from cheap and
440 readily available components from the local drug stores.

441 The lab also produced face masks using appropriate local fabric and prototyped an automatic gel and
442 water dispenser to limit the spread of the virus and encourage frequent washing of hands. Educational
443 aspects were embedded in most activities of the lab. Through the use of the automatic gel dispenser
444 the local population was taught about the importance of handwashing and how an effective hand
445 washing exercise should be carried out. These sensitization sessions were also used to educate the
446 population about the Coronavirus, its modes of transmission, ways of prevention - helping to do
447 away with certain myths about the virus that circulated in the local community.

448 Again, global networks were important to connect with other populations to share stories, knowledge,
449 and approaches using platforms like Openair and Wikifactory. National and international
450 collaboration was encountered in the search of testing kits, and by participating in the development
451 and testing of simple, easy to replicate methods of fighting COVID-19 in resource constraint settings.

452 In spite of all these efforts made, some challenges were encountered. Upscaling was an issue, due to
453 a lack of funds. For instance, the automatic gel dispenser that was prototyped was intended to be kept
454 in at least 10 major centers of the community to encourage frequent washing of hands and
455 demonstrate an efficient hand washing practice. The general increase in prices of all essential and
456 non-essential goods made life difficult for the common local population. The widely spread belief
457 that Africans are naturally immune to the virus and that some concoctions can provide them stronger
458 immunity and protect them from being infected was another hurdle. Part of the population also
459 strongly believed and went about saying that the Coronavirus is not real and that it was only a scam
460 or some "thing" created to deceive and control people's lives.

461 Given the sensitizations, training, and collaborations achieved during this period of the pandemic, the
462 population, community biologists, and makers stand a chance of independently handling future
463 pandemics or epidemics by confidently producing PPE or other materials that might be required to
464 fight the pandemic. The approach is to educate and equip the population with the skills to be able to
465 handle the crisis without depending on the government, non-profit-organisations, or foreign aiders.

466 **5.3 The Dutch Case (WAAG, Amsterdam)**

467 The maker space at Waag aimed to provide support in maker research, product development and
468 prototyping during the first lockdown phase, teaming up with a nationwide group of Technical
469 Universities, the TechMed Center (University of Twente), the police, the Royal Netherlands Army
470 and national and global maker communities.

471 In an attempt to better understand the needs within the medical field efforts were mostly dedicated to
472 coordinating and backchanneling within the network. Via online meetings Waag functioned as a
473 catalyst in bringing different maker groups together and has been connecting stakeholders that
474 weren't in contact or collaboration with each other. It was important to get an overview of products
475 or prototypes that were needed most, but also looking into existing solutions or solutions that were
476 being developed, and how Waag could be involved in this. One of the main concerns and also the
477 main challenge for the Waag team was to ensure the safety of the PPE. Also, getting prototypes
478 tested by certified bodies was difficult. Based on the experiences from other makerspaces in the
479 Netherlands and internationally, door handles and face shields were mostly considered for
480 production.

481 In collaboration with the police Waag explored the prototyping of door handles, which police officers
482 would use when entering an unknown building. Different production methods were explored to find
483 an alternative for the prototype the police were using, which was 3D printed and consumed quite
484 some time for large scale production. The team at Waag adjusted the model so it could be laser cut,
485 and thus be produced at large scale in a short time. The prototype was tested and functional.
486 However, within the police force few police officers wanted to use a door handle in their daily work.
487 So, the adapted design was in the end not produced. Other products the fablab was experimenting
488 with include a transparent face mask and a DIY respirator.

489 There was a lot of media attention on the lack of PPE for healthcare professionals in the Netherlands.
490 Waag reached out to the medical institutions within the Metropole region of Amsterdam to hear what
491 their needs and wishes were, but in the end the first contacts ended in no specific request for further
492 research or prototyping. Thus, the fablab at Waag started to produce face shields and opened a
493 webshop to sell them at minimal costs to local healthcare professionals, organizations and people
494 working in contact jobs, such as hairdressers, cleaning services, beauticians, nail salons etc. Local
495 residential care organizations that were directly offered these face shields did not show any interest.

496 Overall, the impact of Waag's engagement has been mainly in coordinating and pushing the notion of
497 maker skills towards other domains, rather than organizing and producing PPE. Building on a
498 network of local, national and international organizations, Waag was able to push the added value of
499 maker skills as a driving innovation force. However, when it comes to the production and distribution
500 of large numbers of products Waag was expecting more collaboration with large enterprises, which
501 was not achieved. According to their experience commercial companies are reluctant to take up on
502 the innovative designs and knowledge stemming from the maker communities.

503 Finally, it is worth mentioning that the discussion within the national coordination group, including
504 the Netherlands Royal Army, also touched upon the notion of distributed manufacturing. The idea of
505 setting up a global network of decentralized production facilities, as an immediate response to a
506 healthcare crisis, gained wider attention and will be further discussed in the future. Currently the
507 network of fablabs mostly shares knowledge, skills and blueprints, but could it also be equipped to
508 coordinate a large-scale production of e.g. PPE in the future?

509 **5.4 The Iraqi Case (Science Camp, Basra)**

510 Science Camp, a maker space based in Basra, south of Iraq, is attached to the global maker
511 movement and used to provide innovative solutions by implementing digital fabrication & DIY
512 concepts, armed with the qualified industrial infrastructure. This space was among the first entities in
513 the country that responded to the COVID-19 crisis with innovative solutions. Approximately 13.000
514 protective face shields were produced and distributed for free to the frontline medical staff and other
515 main human resources who provide essential services for healthcare, security, delivery services, etc.
516 In collaboration with local industry, local civil society, and academicians, a response infrastructure
517 was set up taking care of e.g. monitoring the needs of PPE, providing raw materials, communicating
518 with healthcare services, PPE production, PPE distribution, online digital statistics monitoring, and
519 research and development. Medical staff highly appreciated the efforts done by the maker community
520 and requested even more face shields and research into other types of PPE.

521 The design and production process of PPE was adapted to the local context, using locally available
522 raw materials, such as PET plastic sheets used in water packaging factories. Also, the design was
523 adapted to be easy to assemble, with no need for gluing, stapling, or sewing. The digital fabrication
524 techniques applied made the production process use a minimal number of raw materials, and fast,
525 with high quality.

526 All efforts were covered by voluntary contributions from all partners. The raw materials were a
527 donation from the local water factory. The Iraqi government did, however, not support this type of
528 community response and some international NGOs suggested converting the PPE production process
529 into a business rather than a charity crisis response, which was not realized by the maker space due to
530 ethical reasons.

531 Apart from the financial challenges, the Iraqi maker space also encountered other difficulties, related
532 to public administration and logistics. Travel permission forms to procure raw materials, machine
533 maintenance, etc. were partly refused during national lockdown and bureaucratic barriers hindered
534 the distribution of PPE via the official channels of the healthcare authorities.

535 In addition to the high recognition in local and global media, the involved makers got experience in
536 PPE production and legal aspects related to it as well as better insight into the use and availability of
537 raw materials and resources locations. The fast response activities have also shown that the bottom-
538 up social response can work independently from governmental or international aid organizations,
539 avoiding potential conflicts between these organizations.

540 **5.5 The Italian Case (Opendot, Milan)**

541 Italy was Europe's first and one of the most affected nations being hit by the COVID-19 pandemic.
542 The country's most efficient health systems in the Northern regions were about to collapse and
543 hospitals were running out of supplies, including PPEs as well as essential parts for ventilators and
544 other respiratory devices. Triggered by the initiative of a maker who provided a hospital with a 3D
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545 printer and helped to reproduce missing valves, the value of the maker community for the local health

546 infrastructure became visible, and local supply chains of PPE for healthcare staff and other essential
547 workers started to emerge.

548 Local coordination groups played an important role in the distributed production and supply chains.
549 These groups were almost all volunteer-based, almost always within existing communities of people
550 or fablab networks who were already used to working together. The first COVID-19 maker networks
551 in Italy were regional, and they succeeded in responding to local needs as they evolved. This
552 teamwork at local and regional levels paved the way for nationwide coordination across Italy. In the
553 period of just a few days, three different initiatives emerged with similar and complementary
554 objectives. One of those initiatives alone, *Make in Italy*⁷, collected over 500 contacts from makers,
555 small laboratories, startups and fablabs. Their website currently lists over 25,000 items produced and
556 donated. Opendot, a fablab in Milano, *Careables* partner and specialized in working with the
557 healthcare sector, was involved in the national coordination activities from the onset and contributed
558 to overcoming the local medical supply shortage.

559 Italy's response to the health crisis wasn't limited to the grassroots maker movement of hundreds of
560 volunteers and fablabs. Many Italian companies worked closely with active makers, and in some cases,
561 even helped the movement to take off. Also the educational sector was involved as the face shield
562 production model was included in the training of high school students, initiated by the Maker@Scuola
563 project⁸.

564 The case in Italy has shown so far how new local collaborations for digital social innovations can be
565 established. Because of the emergency, various hospitals contacted specialized studios, fablabs, small
566 businesses and startups in order to develop new solutions together. Doctors have started to become
567 co-designers, innovators and makers. In Italy, we find some isolated examples where these
568 emergency-driven collaborations have turned into established collaborations where hospitals, doctors
569 and therapists recognize the value and potential of digital fabrication tools and distributed local
570 production. However, the organizational and structural details of cooperation between makerspaces
571 and the public healthcare system in a more systematic way are still to be explored.

572 **6 Focus group results**

573 In the following chapter the results from the focus group discussion with case representatives from
574 Brazil, Cameroon, and Italy are presented.

575 In a first step, focus group participants were invited to relate their Covid-19 activities to one of the
576 levels of social innovation - the micro, meso, or macro level (see Fig. 4). The two case
577 representatives not present during the focus group were given an individual explanation of the matrix
578 and were likewise asked for a positioning.

579 All three case representatives present during the focus group meeting stated that their COVID-19
580 related activities were in transition from micro to meso level. Thus, cooperation with other
581 organizations became important to meet the social need and not only social but also economic
582 objectives were addressed. The Italian case representative said to have acted on a meso level during
583 the first wave of COVID-19, establishing networks between Italian fablabs and organizations in the
584 need for fabricated health devices; but acted again on a micro level when the emergency situation

585 stopped. Connections with political actors have been established but sustainable links are not in place
586 yet. In the Brazilian case, first sustainable contacts were established with local politicians, who
587 showed interest in the civic engagement taking place in Olinda. Also, the close cooperation with
588 health professionals is still in place, after the first wave. In economic terms, the fablab sells
589 individual face shields, fabricated in their fablab, or whole packages, where e.g. a company is
590 donating 200 face shields. In the Cameroon case the activities were and still are closer to the meso
591 level, as sustainable links to other organizations have been established, mostly related to the
592 educational purpose of the lab.

593 In a second step, the focus group participants discussed two key questions: 1) If they would wish for
594 their COVID-19 activities to sustainably scale from micro, to meso, to macro level; and 2) if yes,
595 under which conditions.

596 All three case representatives shared the same opinion – that scaling their activities at least from the
597 micro level to a more stable macro level is wished for, as there are people in the need of help and this
598 need can be met by the production capacities in fablabs. However, scaling up should take place only
599 under certain conditions and building on certain shared principles and values.

600 Scaling up on the social innovation model should not resemble the scaling up in business terms. It
601 was stated that companies tend to change when they scale, losing contact with local communities,
602 introducing intermediate layers of management, and shifting the focus to financial aspects and
603 maximizing incomes. The risk is that open innovation is not open anymore, but rather owned by a
604 company, thus hindering the innovative groundwork that was originally aimed for by their inventors.
605 So it's fundamental to change the models of scaling up.

606 Case representatives wish to scale the approach and spread the specific knowledge on how to co-
607 design and produce (personalized) healthcare devices with digital fabrication tools. So training other
608 fablabs in how to support health and care is key here, but also the training of local people – first
609 regarding COVID-19 and how to best protect themselves, and second how to cooperate with and
610 make use of fablabs to support their health and well-being.

611 Participants aim for establishing connections and collaboration with other fablabs to scale responses
612 to healthcare professionals and people in need. The Italian experience in this regard shows that
613 creating structured networks of cooperation increases complexity. Fablabs are heterogeneous, have
614 different underlying organizational models and specializations. So not every fablab would be able to
615 produce medical equipment that might work properly in a hospital context. The question is how to
616 deal with this complexity and also raises some doubts that strong networks might result in decreasing
617 visibility and importance of the single node of this network.

618 Legislation issues have to be addressed carefully if medical equipment is the focus of digital
619 fabrication. When producing healthcare products or medical equipment the main aim is to not
620 produce more harm than good. In Cameroon, only certain institutions are allowed to produce
621 medical equipment, thus Mboalab focused on producing products where no strict legislative
622 measures need to be addressed, e.g. producing and making accessible proper disinfectants and
623 providing the knowledge on how to protect oneself from COVID-19. In Brazil, legislation is more
624 flexible, and the close cooperation with health personnel allowed the fablab in Olinda to successfully
625 develop face shields used in medical organizations as well as an open-source model of an aerosol
626 box. Nevertheless, *Careables Olinda* stresses that working for other groups in the need of health and
627 care, might be a good way to strengthen their approach while avoiding complex certification issues.
628 In the Italian case, the emergency situation of the first COVID-19 wave gave room for certain
629 legislative exceptions. Still, producing for hospitals requires meeting high quality criteria and

630 demands for additional aspects like documentation, etc. In times of crisis, the official processes might
631 be too long and exclusive to flexibly react to emergencies, so there is a call for more agile
632 mechanisms that are established and tested beyond the times of crisis. It is wished for more flexibility
633 to test the collaboration between medical institutions and local manufacturers to co-design and
634 produce medical equipment below certain risks or costs. As mentioned above, working with and for
635 disabled people, and offering COVID-19 support that is not medical equipment (e.g. disinfection,
636 etc.) are some of the suggested activity areas that can strengthen sustainable cooperation between
637 local manufacturers and people and organizations in need of health and care devices. Alternative
638 approaches to supporting health and care are key to spread the approach.

639 Additionally, strong local nodes are key to spreading the approach. Working in the health and care
640 sector requires at the one hand trust of people and a diverse set of local organizations, on the other
641 hand it aims to successfully empower local people. Thus, establishing a network of local nodes that
642 adapt to local contexts, link to local organizations and the local community of people in need, is the
643 basis of spreading digital fabrication for health and care.

644 The COVID-19 emergency situation showed how powerful the network of local digital
645 manufacturers can be in flexibly supporting societal needs. Focusing this power of the network to
646 other aspects, like climate change, digital fabrication initiatives can play a key role in successfully
647 supporting social innovation processes. Maker activities can in this regard catalyze the attention to a
648 wider problem, e.g. the climate change and the scaling up should not take place at the cost of the
649 environment. Thus, producing tons of plastics (e.g. in the case of face shields) should be critically
650 reflected and alternative ways of more environmentally friendly production should be sought.

651 7 Summary of findings

652 The two main data collection instruments brought forward complementary findings. While the self-
653 reflection reporting focused on describing the past and current experiences made during the COVID-
654 19 response activities by the makers, the focus group discussion built on these experiences and
655 reflected on future implications for the scaling of the makers' grassroots initiatives. Figure 5
656 summarizes the experiences made by the cases and the learnings and implications these experiences
657 reveal for a potential scaling in the future.

658 From the collected experiences we see how fast the maker community reacted during the health
659 emergency by supplying local healthcare providers with urgently needed PPE and other medical
660 devices. Such **responsive** behavior was strongly enabled by the commitment of local stakeholders on
661 the one hand and the global connectedness on the other hand. By drawing from their local, national
662 and global networks the actors in the makerspaces were able to get rapid access to design templates,
663 material resources and distribution channels. Some of the connections with relevant stakeholders,
664 such as medical staff or local politicians, proved to be rather fragile though. For scaling locally
665 embedded maker activities that address local social needs a strengthening of networks, locally and
666 globally, is important according to our cases.

667 The COVID-19 response of the makers was also **flexible** in adapting to the local contexts. This
668 resulted in localized designs, such as the Brazilian tropical face shield, which was a local adaptation
669 of a German design, or the use of locally available materials, such as the Iraqi PET plastic sheet,
670 which are usually used for water packaging. In the case of the Cameroon maker space the COVID-19
671 response activities included a strong educational aspect acknowledging the local need for more
672 information about the virus. Next to the importance of education and training on maker skills, the
673 cases also highlight the strong local embedding and connectedness to the local communities as
674 essential for a flexible and fast response to pressing social issues. For a future scaling of maker space

675 activities that respond locally to social needs established cooperation with local stakeholders has
676 been identified as a key element.

677 Another important aspect addressed in the self-reflection and the focus group discussion has been the
678 awareness for a **responsible** practice from makers. Across the five cases we observe a strong sense of
679 social responsibility. This has been manifested in acknowledgement of quality standards for
680 healthcare products as well as the overall commitment to doing no harm and user safety. Clear
681 guidelines and legal structures that allow responsible making are thus being requested based on the
682 current experiences. When discussing ethical aspects, the case representatives also stress their
683 growing awareness towards the need for ecologically sustainable maker practices.

684 Finally, the case representatives are aware of the **limitations** of the approach. Their COVID-19
685 response activities were limited in terms of capacities, resources, and infrastructures. The makers
686 thus recognize the boundaries of what can be achieved within their limited spaces. Collaboration with
687 established businesses and governments should be envisioned for the future. This would allow for an
688 effective response at a larger scale.

689 **8 Discussion**

690 The five cases represented in this study are located across three continents and are embedded in very
691 different contexts, economically, politically, and socially. When the COVID-19 pandemic started to
692 spread, these makerspaces took on the challenge of counteracting the PPE and medical device
693 shortages. In their civic reactions to the failures of public healthcare procurement and shortages in the
694 global supply chains, they all faced some similar challenges and new opportunities. In this analysis,
695 we want to concentrate on four main perspectives that evolved during the analysis and turned out to
696 be relevant when discussing the maker COVID-19 response activities in the theoretical frame of the
697 three social innovation levels: social needs (micro level), societal challenges (meso level), and
698 systemic changes (macro level).

699 *1. A network perspective*

700 Working in translocal networks, referring to networks at local and global level, has been a critical
701 aspect for the operation on the ground. We saw that reflected in all of the cases, with local networks
702 playing a key role in all phases, from research and design to the production, testing and distribution
703 of the provided COVID-19 response solutions. The established local networks and temporary
704 partnerships include stakeholders from across the quadruple helix, namely academia, government,
705 civil society, and industry. In addition, in most cases, the fast reaction from the makerspaces was
706 only possible due to the global open sharing of PPE designs. Being globally connected offers access
707 to a wide range of resources and is possible only in a culture of openness and sharing, which is
708 propagated also by the Open Design and Open Hardware movements. The benefits of open
709 networked collaborations become visible immediately in times of crisis, such as the COVID-19
710 pandemic. In social transformative innovation theory translocal networks are an important element
711 contributing to empowerment (Avelino et al. 2019). From the reported experiences in the five cases,
712 we can consider maker communities as local and global networks that exchange resources,
713 experiences, and knowledge at global level, but act at local level to adapt to the specific contexts and
714 react to local needs. This ability and commitment for open global collaboration and mutual learning
715 is described as one of the unique features of the global maker movement (Smith 2017) and also
716 implies a certain ethical commitment of the contributing makerspaces. The cases contributing to this
717 study confirm their potential for empowerment as suggested by (Avelino et al. 2019) and resilience
718 of the local actors, similar to what has been encountered by Wuyts et al. (2020).

719 The sustainability of the emergent translocal networks is however very fragile. The Italian case
720 showed that highly efficient and quickly established networks might become loose when the
721 emergency situation is over. For the networks to continue and possibly lead to a transformational
722 change as described by Avelino et al. (2017) new objectives for collaboration that foster a sustainable
723 linkage between network members are needed. For future emergency situations these flexibly
724 emerging translocal networks and partnerships, that have already been installed in previous
725 situations, might help to react even faster.

726 2. *A value perspective*

727 An ethical commitment of the makerspaces becomes noticeable also in other aspects. When
728 discussing ways to scale their practices a need for new types of business models and new value
729 definitions was expressed. Transformative social innovations cannot be achieved by just applying
730 existing innovation models and capabilities to issues of social concern (Smith 2017). It needs a
731 redefinition of values (Avelino et al. 2017) and a redistribution of innovation capabilities. Globally
732 distributed local manufacturing processes need to be assessed on a different level than large
733 enterprises. Next to the purely economic value, which is still dominating in the entrepreneurial
734 context and also present in many maker space activities, we need to appreciate other values, often
735 social and ecological values, that are associated with local experimentation and small-scale
736 production in makerspaces. The ecological footprint of manufacturing is a concern for many makers
737 as we have seen documented e.g. in the Brazilian case. We can deduct that we find within the activist
738 approaches of makers an environmental conscious reflection and self-critical view on their material
739 productive engagement as confirmed by others (e.g. Richertich 2020, Smith 2017). Wuyts et al.
740 (2020) likewise recognise the value of maker activities during the pandemic in moving towards a
741 more circular economy in the healthcare sector.

742 With the presented experiences we argue that environmentally and socially responsible making
743 should be assigned additional value, next to the cost-benefit calculations dominating today's business
744 models and move to added value-oriented models. The case representatives in this study follow a
745 community-driven approach, not a business-driven approach, which needs higher societal
746 recognition. There are attempts to raise broader attention for the values of transformative social
747 innovations in measurable terms, such as the Social Return on Investment (SROI), which is a
748 performance measurement tool, demonstrating the social value enterprises generate. SROI is however
749 an underused and undervalued practice despite being accepted as an internationally recognized
750 measurement tool for social enterprise (Millar & Hall 2012). For community-driven approaches in
751 makerspaces new value models for scaling are needed as the makerspaces of this study clearly do not
752 want to follow the prevailing economic model of scale dominated by monetary value.

753 3. *An educational perspective*

754 Makerspaces are often characterized as spaces for collaboration, information sharing, reflection and
755 learning (Sheridan et al, 2014). Incidental as well as intentional learning takes place in these settings
756 as they are often linked with creativity, collaborative problem solving, digital competence, and
757 entrepreneurship (Vuorikari et al. 2019). An educational agenda was stressed in the Cameroon case,
758 where an important objective of the lab's COVID-19 response activities was to educate the local
759 population in terms of hygiene measures. The other case representatives emphasized the importance
760 of education in their activities generally, and specifically in terms of scaling social innovations.

761 Also, learning between makerspaces and with and from other network partners, like health
762 professionals, is key. We see knowledge exchange on a global scale that addresses overarching
763 topics, like the exchange of certified, proven PPE instruction guides, guidelines on the design of co-

764 creation processes, and the efficient use of digital fabrication tools. And we can identify
765 contextualized knowledge that emerges in the diverse settings, like how to react to the local
766 availability of material, how to adapt production processes to local contexts, how to address very
767 specific local needs. Undoubtedly, the learning taking place in makerspaces leads to empowerment
768 and resilience (Criado et al. 2016; Unterfrauner et al. 2020). As Ratto (2011) identified learning as
769 core in his critical making theory, where the process of making is as important as the results, we also
770 suggest that more societal recognition could be added to the educational value created in
771 makerspaces. Critical skills acquired during the material exploration contribute to the empowerment
772 of the individuals as well as the community. Again, we see similarities here to the cases of
773 empowerment analysed in detail by Avelino et al. (2017). Learning and practicing new skills in
774 social spaces are key elements for empowerment and contribute to the transformative potential of
775 social innovations.

776 4. *A legal perspective*

777 In order for local manufacturing to become relevant at a systemic level, fundamental transformations
778 of the underlying structures need to take place. In the context of open healthcare, current legal
779 frameworks are one of the key structures that would require adaptation. As system changes are
780 typically slow and require long-term thinking, makers are exploring the current boundaries in their
781 support of the healthcare sector. Part of the current boundaries being explored by makers relate to the
782 nature of the solutions they produce. In some states (e.g. in the European Union) the production of
783 specific solutions - such as respiratory valves or breathing masks - requires complex processes and
784 compliance documentation. These are necessary as the solutions qualify as medical devices and
785 imply the respect of the relevant laws in the matter (such as the EU MDD, in the European territory).
786 While the role of these regulations is to ensure a high level of patients' safety and protection, they set
787 approval mechanisms and controls that are not always compatible with emergency situations. In
788 some countries, competent authorities allowed for emergency use authorization for certain
789 technologies (FDA, 2020). As Pearce (2020: 12) noted, many regulatory roadblocks remain across
790 several countries, which may need to be improved to allow rapid response and provision of medical
791 supplies in healthcare emergencies.

792 A second kind of boundary relies on liability mechanisms for makers in the context of emergency
793 situations. As illustrated in the introduction, in a known case some makers reverse-engineered the
794 design of a respiratory valve to face a product shortage in an Italian hospital, which led the original
795 manufacturer to threaten bringing legal action against them for intellectual property infringement.
796 This example explicates the difficult value balance between the perceived need to act (even
797 'ethically') by makers vis-a-vis the possible unintended negative consequences of such ethical acting.
798 As a way forward, so-called *Good Samaritan Laws* - which offer protection from liability for those
799 whom they believe to be in peril, ill, or otherwise incapacitated - could set useful measures to
800 counterbalance this dichotomy. This legal perspective could help reduce the barriers for companies
801 and makers hindering the release of healthcare projects' designs and their replication. The case of
802 COVID19 opened new scenarios for the application of these laws. We are aware of the complexity of
803 system innovation as they are "profound transformations in social systems" (Grin et al., 2010) and
804 we believe that we are still far from seeing innovations being fully implemented in our current legal
805 systems, but the recent experiences during COVID-19 have started to challenge the current
806 boundaries. Thus, future exploration, both in research and by policymakers is needed (Pearce 2020:
807 12) and it would be capable of opening new perspectives for the makerspaces and the role of makers.

808 9 **Conclusion**

809 The experience brought forward in our five contextually very different cases has shown how local
810 production networks can function in times of emergency. Their local design, production, and
811 distribution of PPE and other healthcare related products towards health professionals and the general
812 population has proven to flexibly cover emerging needs and stand in for global manufacturers.
813 Looking at the makers' initiatives during the COVID-19 crisis from a social and transformative
814 innovation perspective, we encounter a wish to scale from working on the social needs level to
815 addressing wider societal demands and, in the future, even triggering systemic change. Networking
816 and sharing knowledge and experiences across multiple actors are key with this aim. Representatives
817 from the five cases stress the importance of emergent translocal networks for their COVID-19
818 response to happen, which include actors of the quadruple helix on local scale while exchanging and
819 learning from each other globally.

820 Scaling transformative practices of makerspaces is however envisioned only under certain
821 circumstances and following a set of principles and values. A commitment towards openness and
822 sharing, such as it is propagated by the open hardware movement, requires new forms of business
823 and value models. Prototyping in the healthcare domain, with and for patients, people with
824 disabilities, and other often vulnerable groups, requires an ethical commitment and legal backing in
825 order not to produce more harm than good. Educational and environmental considerations likewise
826 come into play. Empowerment through teaching and creating only solutions that address real
827 personal problems or needs are core principles of responsible making. In the makers' future
828 endeavors towards co-designing and making open, personalized healthcare and establishing these
829 processes as social innovations more social value propositions may be encountered, with implications
830 for individuals, communities and society at large. While we notice signs of empowerment at
831 individual and community level, we envision a strengthening of democratic processes at society
832 level. Other scholars likewise speak about the democratic value of makerspaces, which they find in
833 certain grassroots activities that address social issues (e.g. Taylor et al. 2016, Willingham 2017,
834 Sipos et al. 2019). At the same time, we are aware of the critical views some scholars express
835 towards makerspaces. Lindtner et al. (2016) challenge the democratization potential of the maker
836 movement and suggest a more self-critical and reflexive approach for the whole community of
837 makers. We hope this study can contribute to the discussion.

838 We have considered implications that go beyond the makers' response to fighting COVID-19 from
839 the experiences made in five contextually diverse settings. We are aware of the limitations of our
840 study, but see reasonable generalization justified by the contextual heterogeneity of the cases
841 covered, the strong embeddedness and connectedness of the case representatives (and co-authors)
842 with the global maker community, and the similarities we have found on other documented cases,
843 such as those documented by others. Our case-based snapshots resonate well with other documented
844 experiences (e.g. Richterich 2020, Diez & Baeck 2020). Next to this qualitative approach a more
845 systematic and quantitative assessment of the impact that the maker communities worldwide had on
846 fighting the COVID-19 pandemic is needed. In how far has the global maker response during the
847 COVID-19 emergency situation created sustainable impact and have longer-term linkages between
848 local manufacturers and health care services been created? Also, we would love to see more
849 explorations of how and under which conditions makerspaces contribute to addressing societal
850 challenges and how these may trigger systemic change in the future.

851 **10 Conflict of Interest**

852 *The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
853 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

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859 effort to establish *Careables* as a global reference for the co-design, making and sharing of open,
860 personalized healthcare for everyone.

861 **13 References**

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982 **Table 1**

original codes	sub-codes	grouped codes
partnerships	collaboration	networks, partnerships, collaborations
networks (local, regional, national, global)		
collaboration with healthcare professionals		
collaboration with educational sector		
relationship with healthcare sector		
national & international collaboration		
collaboration with companies and industry		
collaboration with specific target groups, e.g. police, army		
coordination of local groups	coordination	

coordination of national activities	challenges in networks	value, scale, infrastructures
decreasing visibility in large networks		
increased complexity of structured networks		
not losing contact to local communities		
lacking cooperation with government		
local context adaption	local embedding	
local aspects		
local coordination groups		
local needs		
scaling	scale	
upscaling		
shared principles, values	values	
voluntary contributions, volunteers		
political support		
power of networks		
flexibility		
trust		
sustainability	sustainability	
business models		
funding		
platforms	infrastructures	
local infrastructure		
communication		
logistics		
logal supply chains		

national coordination		
structured networks		
overcoming barriers in the production (material, legal & ethical aspects)	challenges of infrastructures	
lack of resources, e.g. material		
lack of funding		
sensitisation		
local and international awareness		
education	education	
skills, experiences		
exchange of knowledge		
tackling misconceptions		
guidance	training	
training		
empowerment of citizens	skills	
pushing maker skills towards other domains, e.g. health-sector		
critical thinking of negative impact		
safety	safety	safety, quality, legal aspects
quality, certification	quality	
prototyping & testing		
legal aspects (national & international)	legal aspects	

983

984 **Figure legend**

985 Figure 1: Adaption of the three BEPA (2010) levels of social innovation

986 Figure 2: Steps of data collection and analysis

987 Figure 3: Scale and social innovation matrix (adapted from Unterfrauner et al. 2020)

988 Figure 4: Case positioning on scale and social innovation matrix

989 Figure 5: COVID-19 maker response and learnings

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

